

Mengingat Genosida '65:
Remembering the Anti-Communist Genocide of *Orde Baru* Indonesia

DISSERTATION

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Untuk Ibu-Ibu, Bapak-Bapak penyintas '65

Untuk semua yang terus berjuang

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Abstract

This thesis examines the state of collective memory of Orde Baru Indonesia's anti-communist genocide and the act of reclaiming collective memory from hegemony. Using archival research and ethnographic fieldwork of memory sites in Yogyakarta and Bali, the study explores the hegemony of the state sponsored G30S metanarrative over the collective memory of state violence, further legitimising the regime. It argues that remembering is central in reclaiming collective memory of violence from hegemony, respecting the understanding that having multiple diverse narratives is what defines collective memory. Personal and social dimensions to remembering are required to publicly engage with Indonesia's complex past. This thesis seeks to contribute to broader discussions on memory politics in post-authoritarian societies and the ongoing struggle for historical justice in Indonesia.

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Introduction

The memory of Indonesia's *Orde Baru*¹ regime has its own seat in my family's dinner table. Remnants of violence created throughout the three decades-long military regime led by Suharto continues to thrive within the post-authoritarian society, affecting ways people interact with each other, how places are remembered, and the country's politics. I remember that in my childhood I would not meander from mentioning that I was spending time with the grandmothers who are survivors to the 1965 tragedy, from talking about how my father was kidnapped by the Suharto's government. Consequently, it created a constant disconnect between me and my peers. It was that early that I learnt that talking about the violence, mass killings, rapes, tortures that occurred throughout Orde Baru is not the favourite past time of most Indonesians.

Despite the transition to a more democratic regime of Reformasi (1998-onwards), many of those who were involved in the commanding level of various Orde Baru violence are still virtually unaffected by their past level of complicity working in executive-level politics (ministries, presidential).

An explicit and recent example can be observed from the most recent 2024 presidential election. Prabowo Subianto managed to exploit the politicisation of memory in favour of his background and identity for his political campaign. Despite being dismissed from his position in the military (then: ABRI) due to his complicity in the student activists kidnappings of 1998, among others, Prabowo ran for president for the third consecutive times in the general election.² Claiming those and generally the act of "dwelling on the past"

¹ Orde Baru (translated: New Order) regime is the second political regime to Indonesia, marked by Suharto's rule. It lasted from 1965-1998 and is the regime between Orde Lama (Old Order regime) of founding father Sukarno and Reformasi (Reform regime). Hereafter, the regimes will not be written in italics.

² William, 'Ini Alasan Prabowo Dipecat Sebagai Perwira'; indonotes, 'The Verdict on Prabowo Subianto – A Translation'; The Jakarta Post, 'Fresh Doubt Cast on Prabowo's Suitability to Rule';

stunts people from growing to the future, he rebranded his character through social media, notably TikTok by engineering a “cute” image through avatars among others.³ As such, Prabowo managed to secure his position as the President following the 2024 election with the abundant of political controversies riddling every part of his campaign.⁴

It is an interesting time to be writing this while watching in real time how memory politics are being practised in the highest level within the country. Discussions surrounding memory of Orde Baru is getting “tired”, overused, like a dead horse beaten to the ground—or so goes the sentiments shared by many young Indonesians.

The question is what happens when the majority of a collective does not care for their own memory?

I do not judge this fatigue, or what I would also refer to as fear, of memory of violence or human rights abuse as invalid. I believe that it is commonplace as a country that has seen how memory is politicised for the purpose of controlling public opinions and fulfil group’s interest (particularly the elite). However, such aversion to memory would only enable a generation that is short-sighted and to abandon the past is to not learn from the pain it has held and continue to exude in the coming decades.

Memory is not an object one, lest a society, can avoid. Per Leksana’s recent work I adopt that memory is a historical process that is affected by the ceaseless uncovering of the

Matanasi, ‘Kata DKP Prabowo Bersalah’. Oddly enough in 2019, the Ministry of Communications and Informatics (Kominfo) claimed that Prabowo being discharged is disinformation, focusing on the semantic, Kominfo stated that instead Prabowo was moved from his position to be *Komandan Sesko ABRI*. However, this is contradictory to the leaked document of Prabowo’s dismissal from the military in 21 August 1998 which in the end concluded “In accordance with the above, the Examined Officer under the name Lieutenant General (Indonesian Army) Prabowo Subianto is proposed to face administrative sanctions in the form of ending of his military service.”KOMINFO, ‘[DISINFORMASI] Prabowo Dipecat Jadi TNI’.

³ The Economist, ‘TikTok Is a Key Battleground in Indonesia’s Election’; Wahid, ‘Did Prabowo Subianto’s TikTok Makeover Impact the Indonesian Election Results?’; ‘Prabowogemesin (@prabowogemesin) TikTok Account’.

⁴ *D1RTY V0TE*; CNN Indonesia, ‘Jalan Panjang Prabowo Subianto di Pilpres’; BBC News Indonesia, ‘Pemilu 2024’; Tempo, ‘Kekuasaan’.

past.⁵ As well as Wardaya's claim as echoed by Eickhoff on how memory is a relational phenomenon in which narratives dynamically connect individual, groups, and events through time and space.⁶ In such a way, I would like to posit that their understanding and conception of "memory" is itself is what I adopt as "collective memory".

Collective memory is not a singular "truth" but rather a picture taken of the incessant process of many different perceptions of past events. It is dynamic and immaterial. Moreover, memory politics exists at the periphery of memory. Memory politics, as I see it, more so involves the effort to appropriate and regulate memory in a structure or order at the elite's interest. This includes claiming hegemony over collective memory, which is a blatant oxymoron, done through policing what is allowed to be seen as what had happened in the past and deifying a single "true" memory (which again is not an object) or narrative of the past.

The Orde Baru regime sees itself after the military *coup d'état* led by Lieutenant Suharto to overthrow Sukarno, Indonesia's founding president. This transition from Sukarno's Orde Lama regime to Suharto's Orde Baru was not a smooth one, as it arguably became the erupting point of instability of the three most powerful political figures in newfound Indonesia⁷: Sukarno, TNI (the Indonesian National Military), and the Indonesia's Communist Party (PKI) which was the largest communist political party in the world outside of a communist country.⁸

⁵ Leksana, *Memory Culture of the Anti-Leftist Violence in Indonesia*.

⁶ Eickhoff et al., 'The Memory Landscapes of "1965" in Semarang', 513.

⁷ Wardaya, 'Menembus Politik Ingatan', 163; Hardoyo, 'The Future of the Left in Indonesia', 157; Rinakit, 'Military during the Pre-Reform Period', 23; Utrecht, 'The Coup of October 1965 and Aftermath', 164.

⁸ Eickhoff et al., 'The Memory Landscapes of "1965" in Semarang', 536. "PKI developed into the world's largest non-ruling communist party, with 3.5 million members. More than fifteen million people were members of affiliated organizations, such as BTI (Barisan Tani Indonesia/Indonesian Peasants' Front), SOBSI (Sentral Organisasi Buruh Seluruh Indonesia/All-Indonesian Labour Union), the Pemuda Rakjat (People's Youth) and Gerwani (Gerakan Wanita Indonesia/Indonesian Women's Movement)."

In late September 1965, the kidnapping and subsequent killings of seven TNI generals was pinned on the PKI through a TNI-crafted narrative which was enforced throughout Orde Baru. As such, Indonesians got to know the kidnapping as a cruelty enacted by the PKI through mainstream and textbook history⁹, which is apparent by the title of this narrative framing: “G30S/PKI”, the “G30S” referring to the “Movement of 30th September”, while the “/PKI” to ensure that its connection to PKI is remembered. With the G30S/PKI construction TNI, led by Suharto was able to launch a fully justified extermination on a vaguely wide profile of PKI members, sympathisers, and later whoever opposing the military government.

As news from Jakarta of the kidnappings through the G30S/PKI narrative spread, so did the extermination of the loose profile of PKI members. The killings quickly escalated into a genocide, primarily facilitated by TNI, with systemic killings of people all over the country, rape, forced labour, and many others forms of violence that later follows well into the current Reformasi regime.¹⁰ The numbers of those killed is estimated to be around 800’000 to 1’200’000 people between the one-year period of what is now publicly known as “*Peristiwa 1965-1966*” (The Event of 1965-1966).¹¹

Faithfully, on 11 March 1966 came the infamous *Supersemar* (The Letter of Instructions of Eleventh March), a now-lost document signed by Sukarno that supposedly enabled the transfer of Sukarno’s executive power to Suharto, which would then be used by Suharto to outlaw PKI.¹²

⁹ Eddyono, ‘The Shift in the Regime of Silence’; Supriatma, ‘Kata Pengantar: G30S, PKI, Dan Pembunuhan Massal’, 2.

¹⁰ Pohlman, ‘Sexual Violence as Torture’; Wieringa and Katjasungkana, *Propaganda and the Genocide in Indonesia*; Kusumaningrum et al., ‘Sites of Violence, Sites of Peace, Sites of Justice’, 313.

¹¹ Robinson, ‘The Killing Season’; Melvin, *The Army and the Indonesian Genocide*.

¹² Rinakit, ‘Military during the Pre-Reform Period’, 25.

Interestingly, *Peristiwa 1965-1966* is not popularly referred to when one talks about the marker of Orde Baru's beginning, but rather it would be G30S/PKI or *Supersemar*.

Although Orde Baru, has had its share of authoritarian state violence, *Peristiwa 1965-1966* is what I define as the starting point of the memory of Orde Baru state violence. Note that the vague title of "*Peristiwa*" in Indonesia translates to "event" and is commonly used to address other human rights violations in Indonesia as an attempt to ameliorate the memory violence. Hereafter the "event" will be referred to as **Genosida '65** (the 1965 genocide), a term commonly used by those fighting for the reparation and addressal of the massacres.¹³

The construction of collective memory of state violence continues to remain a battle, even in Reformasi era Indonesia with its democratic identity. As of 2024, Indonesia's conception of dealing with past atrocities can be seen divided into two aspects, judicial and non-judicial.

Judicial proceedings have yielded less than satisfactory results to the victims and their families. In total, Indonesia has held ad-hoc human rights courts for four tragedies: Timor Leste, the Tanjung Priok 'Incident', Papua 2001, and the most recent proceedings being the Paniai 'Incident' 2014.¹⁴ Numerous flaws on the process have been pointed out, the most jarring is on its own premise being that they are judicial proceedings against the

¹³ If I were to be more specific it would be politicide, however this thesis is not a legal document hence all semantics are chosen primarily by my own volition. For me, it is important as it diminishes the end year of the genocide as 1966, since systemic violence that is not properly addressed will continue to persist even after the deaths of all personally involved. The capital "G" letter is also a deliberate choice to denote and uncomfortably exemplify the word between the sentences, reflecting the memory of violence it carries that tends to be brushed off in everyday Indonesia.

¹⁴ BBC News Indonesia, 'Kasus Paniai, Papua'; Koalisi Masyarakat Sipil Pemantau Paniai 2014, 'Sidang Pemeriksaan Saksi Kedua Pengadilan HAM Peristiwa Paniai 2014'; Koalisi Masyarakat Sipil Pemantau Paniai 2014, 'Tanggapan Masyarakat Sipil Terhadap Putusan Pengadilan HAM Paniai'; Koalisi Masyarakat Sipil Pemantau Paniai 2014, 'Tanggapan Koalisi Masyarakat Sipil Terhadap Vonis Bebas Pengadilan HAM Paniai'; Koalisi Masyarakat Sipil Pemantau Paniai 2014, 'Sidang Pemeriksaan Saksi Pertama Pengadilan HAM Atas Peristiwa Paniai 2014'; Purnamasari, 'Pengadilan HAM Paniai yang Masih Jauh Panggang dari Api'; LBH Papua, '013/SP-LBH-Papua/XII/2022: Putusan Bebas Kasus Pelanggaran HAM Berat Paniai Bukti Negara Tidak Memiliki Komitmen Pemenuhan Hak Atas Keadilan Bagi Korban'.

state (in the form of individuals, mostly from the military, acting as extension of the states by proxy of their occupation or position at the time of the atrocity), organised and managed by the state.¹⁵

Similarly, non-judicial efforts attempted by the state to address the past seems to invoke emotional responses by state officials (many who are of the military) and its people respectively. As notable examples, Indonesian non-judicial state efforts to address past violence can be seen in two distinct instances.

First is through the adopted transitional justice paradigm, which can be most clearly seen in the case of the Commission of Truth and Reconciliation (KKR) in Aceh since 2016 that is still ongoing. Due to the KKR law being repealed by the Constitutional Court (MK) resulting to failure to reach the national level and KKR's prescribed permanence, despite truth commission supposedly being temporary, KKR Aceh's has yielded only limited meaningful impact.¹⁶

Second notable instance of non-judicial effort done by the Indonesian state is through public statements issued by the president. The sole and only known apology issued by an incumbent Indonesian president was an apology stated by Abdhurahmann Wahid (Gus Dur)¹⁷ on TVRI (the national Indonesian TV network) for the "killings of communists and its sympathisers", referring to Genosida '65.¹⁸ Boldly, he then doubled down to

¹⁵ Buana, 'A Realistic Perspective to Transitional Justice: A Study of Its Impediments in Indonesia'; McGregor and Setiawan, 'Shifting from International to "Indonesian" Justice Measures'; Wahyuningroem, 'Towards Post-Transitional Justice: The Failures of Transitional Justice and the Roles of Civil Society in Indonesia'; Hutagalung, 'Negara dan Pelanggaran HAM Masa Lalu: Tuntutan Pertanggungjawaban versus Impunitas'; Fadhil, 'Impunitas Dan Penerapan Keadilan Transisi'.

¹⁶ Buana, 'A Realistic Perspective to Transitional Justice: A Study of Its Impediments in Indonesia', 420; Wardaya, 'Menembus Politik Ingatan', 174.

¹⁷ Gus Dur was also the leader of the biggest Muslim organisation in Indonesia Nahdatul Ulama (NU) who reformed NU in the '80s. He is known not just as a political figure, but also an Islamic religious leader. This makes his apology even more powerful, as one of the main anti-communists framing in Indonesia is through religion and how NU was one of the many religious actors complicit in Genosida '65.

¹⁸ Pranata, 'Gus Dur Dan Permintaan Maaf Atas Pembantaian 1965'; *G30S 1965, Cerita Gus Dur Minta Maaf Sampai Tahanan Politik Era Suharto*.

question whether it is appropriate to kill all communists without trial. In his lifetime, he also publicly pressed for historical clarification on Indonesia's G30S history, stating that G30S was not a communist *coup-de-état*.¹⁹ To this day, Gus Dur's apology is still the only instance that a president has referred to the killing of communists, in the context of 1965, as something virtually inappropriate or morally negative.

Seemingly learning from Gus Dur's apology, in 2022, reigning President Joko 'Jokowi' Widodo issued a public statement acknowledging twelve human rights abuses in Indonesia's past, Genosida '65 being the oldest one addressed.²⁰ Jokowi's public statement was preceded by the assemblage of Team for Non-Judicial Resolution of Past Gross Human Rights Violations (*Tim PPHAM*). Tim PPHAM was responsible for constructing and structuring the report that ultimately categorised 12 atrocities in the past under the term of gross violations of human rights (*pelanggaran HAM berat*), which was released publicly by Jokowi on 11 January 2023. As of the writing of this thesis, these are the only two instances in which Indonesia's president issued an official public statement of regret regarding past violence.

On the other side, non-judicial efforts have also been taken by non-state actors through multiple avenues. A notable example is the establishment of the International Peoples Tribunal (IPT '65) in the Hague, Netherlands in 2016. IPT '65 concluded the massacres that happened from 1965 may have amounted for it to be appropriately identified as a genocide, specifically a *politicide* (political genocide).²¹ Such example contributed to the communal project of reclaiming the collective memory of Genosida '65

¹⁹ *Gus Dur*.

²⁰ 'KESBANGPOL - Daftar Pelanggaran HAM Berat Yang Diakui Oleh Presiden Jokowi'.

²¹ IPT 1965, 'Final Report of the IPT 1965: Findings and Documents of the International People's Tribunal on Crimes against Humanity Indonesia 1965', 74–76.

alongside efforts such as recompiling documentations, creation of documentaries or movies that enter mainstream market, the writing of memoirs.

Nevertheless, challenges to address the past, specifically Genosida '65, prevails. To this year of 2024, Indonesia continues to harbour TAP MPRS No. XXV/MPRS/1966, a law outlawing "the spread of communist ideology," a prominent remnant from the Orde Baru regime.²² Exploiting legal loopholes, the law enables the state to maintain control over the dominant narrative of the violence that happened in Orde Baru, including Genosida '65 narrative, and limit spaces for critical discussions of politics.²³ Numerous records detailing the violence during Orde Baru fell victim to destruction.

Many surviving records are scattered across foreign archives, predominantly in Europe, for different reasons based on the archive donators and Indonesians archivists. Some being that Indonesia has yet to have adequate capacity to properly preserve archives, while others citing fear that due to the TAP MPRS No. XXV/MPRS/1966 the documents would be deliberately destroyed. Although providing a sense of security, this restricted access to Orde Baru archives presents a formidable obstacle for various endeavours ranging from the general accessibility to Indonesian public to more specific as aspired judicial procedure, research initiatives, and the preservation of collective memory through documentation. All of which are related to the collective memory of Orde Baru.

What good are archives if only a select few people can access it. Just as what good are scientific papers if they are paywalled. I fear that this limited access to documentations

²² TAP MPRS Nomor XXV/MPRS/1966 tentang Pembubaran Partai Komunis Indonesia, Pernyataan Sebagai Organisasi Terlarang di Seluruh Wilayah Negara Republik Indonesia bagi Partai Komunis Indonesia dan Larangan Setiap Kegiatan untuk Menyebarkan atau Mengembangkan Paham atau Ajaran Komunisme/Marxisme-Leninisme tidak dicabut atau masih berlaku; Until now, Gus Dur remains the only person whose effort was closest enough to revoking the TAP MPRS No. XXV/MPRS/1966 with the basis of the law being unconstitutional and against plurality/diversity.

²³ Pamungkas, 'The Generation That Breaks the Silence'.

of the past would only mirror the state of collective memory during the Orde Baru regime, in which access to the country's past is only accessible to a very limited number of people. In such situation, collective memory would lose its cardinal character of being a collective process in which people of the country can contribute to and access.²⁴

Throughout Reformasi, Indonesia has taken incremental steps towards addressing past crimes, yet the possibility to challenge prevailing dominant narratives of past violence remains insufficient. The amalgamation of these challenges underscores the complexity and urgency of addressing historical gaps and for a more comprehensive understanding of Indonesia's past. Perhaps it is good to reflect on the country's motto of "*Bhinneka Tunggal Ika*" that champions the wholeness of diversity²⁵, in the practice of treating the country's collective memory. Writing this thesis, challenging the memory of Genosida '65 to take its appropriate space within the Indonesian collective memory and allowing for Indonesians to reclaim access to collective memory if they so choose.²⁶

In the face of these challenges, I posit that the act of reclaiming Orde Baru collective memory does not entail a singular climatic instance, but rather a long process that consist of two layers: personal and social. Personal as in intention, in which you need to want to remember.²⁷ Social as in interacting, discussing, and listening to those around us. Rather than merely replacing one overarching narrative with another, the thesis suggests for the diversification of perspectives and narratives of past violence through the act of

²⁴ By access I mean the ability to either discuss their memory and others of past events without the risk of persecution.

²⁵ The motto is in Old Javanese. Popularly translated in English as "Unity in Diversity", but the Indonesian popular translation is "*berbeda-beda, tetapi tetap satu*". I feel as though the English counterpart lacks nuance and therefore offer the wording of "wholeness" in the thesis.

²⁶ Also noting that access to Orde Baru collective memory differs depending on locality and individual context and backgrounds, as eloquently explored by Leksana, *Memory Culture of the Anti-Leftist Violence in Indonesia*.

²⁷ Remembering itself is not just about our own past, but also what had happened in the past based on others' personal narratives.

remembering in order to reclaim certain collective memory. In other words, the essence of reclaiming collective memory lies in acknowledging the complex, multi-layered reality of human experiences, allowing for collective memory to stay true to its name. It underscores the importance of embracing the nuanced, multi-layered reality of human experiences to shape a more collective memory.

The exploration begins by addressing the boundary set for this thesis which is Genosida '65 as the temporal marker of the dawn of the Orde Baru. Foremost, through this deliberate choice, I actively reject and shift the dominant state-endorsed narrative that pinpoints the beginning of Orde Baru regime with the kidnappings of generals. Rather, I replace it with the systemic anti-communist killings and violence that started soon after and acts as a prequel to *Supersemar*. Additionally, as part of rejecting the embedded propaganda of linking the G30S kidnapping and PKI, I will refer to the kidnapping as "G30S" and the narrative that is constructed and preserved by Suharto's Orde Baru as "G30S metanarrative" instead of "G30S/PKI". Within this first chapter, I will explore the concept of collective memory hegemony by discussing the connection between G30S metanarrative and the collective memory of Genosida '65. It explores how the TNI, as one of the three dominant political entities at the time, managed to capture and claim hegemony over what is to be remembered and how the anti-communist genocide and abuse was to be sustained in the state. The second chapter moves our focus to the relationship of memory and space in Indonesia. It follows my journey in Bali and Yogyakarta (with its East Java surroundings) of remembering Genosida '65 violence through memory sites and Leksana's concept of 'embedded memory' through the Genosida '65 community²⁸ and "tours". The third chapter

²⁸ Indonesian resistance against state violence finds its strength in the informal conviviality shared among *penyintas* (survivors or victims), *keluarga korban*, and *kawan* (comrades).

lays out my brief ethnographic archival research on *Perpustakaan Online Genosida '65* (Genosida '65 Online Library), which served as a main online repository I refer to for desk research.

Through this thesis, I seek to contribute to the broader discussion on how post-authoritarian societies can confront state violence through the act of **remembering** (*melawan lupa/resisting forgetting*) as a form of reclaiming collective memory. This thesis does not only serve as an analytical research thesis for my Master's, but also touches on a very delicate personal part of my identity. Undoubtedly, this thesis is meta in a way that it also becomes a display of my personal journey of remembering which I discuss. I think it is important to be straight-forward about that. In doing so, I hope to encourage younger Indonesians to actively partake in analysing Indonesia's memory culture, especially regarding past violence.

It starts from allowing space for discussion and analysis on the most taboo topic of Indonesian history, which is of course subjective and differs from one person to another. From my experience being born in the early days of Reformasi, Genosida '65 is easily the most obscure and socially taboo topic of Orde Baru to discuss. But I am not afraid, and I stand by what I have written here and the semantics I have soberly chosen. As such, I will start here, because only when the nation lets go of its fear of the past and allow for space to discuss them, will the nation, in its wholeness, be able to learn from it.

Literature Review: The Memory Landscape of Orde Baru Indonesia

In this literature review, I focus on three recent works that provide substantial insights into the current discourse of Indonesia's collective memory, specifically on *Genosida '65: Grace Leksana's 'Memory Culture of Anti-Left Violence in Indonesia' (2023)*²⁹; Wieringa and Katjasungkana's *'Propaganda and the Genocide in Indonesia: Imagined Evil' (2018)*³⁰; and Budianta and Tiwon's edited *'Trajectories of Memory: Excavating the Past in Indonesia' (2023)*³¹.

Leksana and Budianta & Tiwon's books both seem to adopt a newer temporal focus of Genosida '65 memory work on the aftermath of violence rather than during the violence itself. Both works seem to address the concern over a unilinear or singular trajectory of collective memory of violence, Leksana specifically referring how if such counternarrative was what we strive for it would be no different that the Orde Baru historiography in the pursuit of creating "one dominant narrative". Similarly, Budianta and Tiwon expresses how the aim is to create a space of plurality of memory works, and later repeating Pramoedya Ananta Toer's³² reflection on what narrating memory means, that writing is not so much about "preserving the past in pristine purity" but rather to "engage with the gaps writing opens up". These works serve as my foundation in analysing the themes surrounding the existing scholarship in Genosida '65 collective memory.

Collective Memory Hegemony

As briefly mentioned in the introduction, I argued that hegemonic control over collective memory creates a paradox through the manipulation of memory politics,

²⁹ Leksana, *Memory Culture of the Anti-Leftist Violence in Indonesia*.

³⁰ Wieringa and Katjasungkana, *Propaganda and the Genocide in Indonesia*.

³¹ Budianta and Tiwon, *Trajectories of Memory*.

³² A famed leftist figure in Indonesia. He is an anti-colonial Indonesian author who was one of the Buru Island political prisoners.

necessitating the efforts to reclaim collective memory. In the context of Genosida '65 collective memory, the hegemonic control I refer to is that of the TNI tracing back to their deliberate construction of the G30S metanarrative as a foundation for Suharto's Orde Baru regime legitimacy, and their consequent effort to vigorously preserve and enforce it.³³ This shows the replacement, rather than destruction, of Genosida '65's memory of sufferings with the constructed G30S metanarrative, as detailed by Wieringa.³⁴ In other words, eclipsing Genosida '65 memory of violence with the metanarrative. Notably, the extent to which the memory of suffering is overshadowed, as well as its persistence, varies by locality. However, these memories, no matter how overshadowed, continue to prevail.³⁵

The logic is that the replacement of memory rather than destruction points to how TNI's G30S metanarrative is utilised as a form of justification or legitimacy for the Genosida '65. Moreover, through this act of replacement, sustaining the metanarrative means that the subsequent anti-communist sentiments can continue to be preserved throughout the Orde Baru regime. G30S metanarrative's hegemony over collective memory does not only dictate the Indonesian memory of communism as a political ideology, but also the transition from Sukarno's Orde Lama to Suharto's Orde Baru. Preservation of the G30S metanarrative shifts the focus of historical account of the regime transition away from the *coup-d'état* and genocide that follows, to the pre-existing anti-communist sentiments fuelled by fear,

³³ McGregor, *History in Uniform*; McGregor, 'Memory Studies and Human Rights in Indonesia'; Leksana and Subekti, 'Remembering through Fragmented Narratives'; Munir, 'The Future of the Civil-Military Relationship in Indonesia'; Robinson, 'The Killing Season'; Tempo, *Pengakuan Algojo 1965: Investigasi Tempo Perihal Pembantaian 1965*; Wieringa and Katjasungkana, *Propaganda and the Genocide in Indonesia*; Roosa, *Pretext for Mass Murder*; Anderson and McVey, 'Cornell Papers'.

³⁴ Wieringa and Katjasungkana, *Propaganda and the Genocide in Indonesia*.

³⁵ Leksana, *Memory Culture of the Anti-Leftist Violence in Indonesia*; Dirgantoro, 'From Silence to Speech'; Supriatma, 'Kata Pengantar: G30S, PKI, Dan Pembunuhan Massal', 2.

hatred, and the mystified face of PKI.³⁶ This concept of collective memory hegemony will further be explored in Chapter 1.

In the G30S metanarrative, the kidnappings are depicted with a specific ritualistic torture including genital mutilation, gouging of eyeballs, while surrounded by PKI members including bare-chested Gerwani (Indonesian Women's Movement) women, emblematic of “the communist woman” in this narrative. Through the depiction of PKI's ritualistic torture, the metanarrative reinforces negative stereotypes of a perverse and non-moralistic character, contributing to the broader dehumanization of communists, especially the women.³⁷ Wieringa and Katjasungkana had touched about this construction of the communist image in Indonesia per *Genosida '65*, to which she highlighted the power of manipulation of emotion through various means of communication (read: propaganda) in fuelling the hateful affective regime over communism in Indonesia. The religious dimension of the anti-communist trope such as non-worshippers or disbelievers of God also particularly propelled the mobilisation of the numerous killings enacted by religious groups within the genocide.³⁸

Moreover, Wieringa highlights how this manipulation of emotions done through propaganda is a form of manifestation of power, as well as the notable censorship instilled on majority newspapers immediately in the first two weeks of October 1965 by the military.³⁹ As previously mentioned, the anti-communist sentiments sustained by the metanarrative and the urgency for the army to maintain domination over the collective

³⁶ Further analysis on the affective regime surrounding the engineering of Genosida '65 would be interesting.

³⁷ Wieringa and Katjasungkana, *Propaganda and the Genocide in Indonesia*.

³⁸ Leksana, 'Collaboration in Mass Violence'; Eddyono, 'The Shift in the Regime of Silence'.

³⁹ Wardaya, 'Menembus Politik Ingatan', 170; Wieringa and Katjasungkana, *Propaganda and the Genocide in Indonesia*.

memory to disproportionately highlight the metanarrative comes off as a pre-emptive defensive justification of the violence that follows after. This hectic urgency of memory politics was further explored by Narwaya who addressed the collective memory of G30S as the building foundation to a politics of forgetting that I believe to continue to shape Indonesia's relationship with memory in Reformasi, as well as other works discussing its utility to legitimise Suharto's military Orde Baru regime.⁴⁰

Silence, traditionally seen as the absence of narrative and a by-product or symptom of suppression within a dictatorship regime, plays a significant role in the collective memory of Genosida '65. Eddyono's work notes how silence is being used forcefully to repress alternative accounts and further impose the dominance of the state-promoted G30S metanarrative.⁴¹ Such systemic silencing imposed in the Orde Baru regime, that essentially erased alternative or opposition ideology by labelling them as communist (and consequently anti-nationalist), has been challenged by the third generation of Genosida '65 families and younger society at large as explored by Pamungkas.⁴²

Eddyono further explored the concept of silence as utilised by the Indonesian state, specifically on educational materials.⁴³ As part of the state effort to maintain the metanarrative legitimacy, Eddyono noted a necessary shift of Suharto's regime's strategy of silence from outright repression of alternative accounts to selective erasure and reframing of historical narrative in school textbooks. In the earlier analysed historical textbooks, Eddyono found that regime transition from Sukarno to Suharto previously focusing on G30S metanarrative as the start to Orde Baru. Meanwhile, the 2008 revision that stated how

⁴⁰ Narwaya, *Kuasa Stigma Dan Represi Ingatan*; Eddyono, 'The Shift in the Regime of Silence', 3; Budiawan, 'When Memory Challenges History'; Sebastian, 'Enframing Indonesian Concepts of National Security', 35; Munir, 'The Future of the Civil-Military Relationship in Indonesia', 71.

⁴¹ Eddyono, 'The Shift in the Regime of Silence'.

⁴² Pamungkas, 'The Generation That Breaks the Silence'.

⁴³ Eddyono, 'The Shift in the Regime of Silence'.

*Supersemar*⁴⁴ marked the start of Orde Baru, thereby omitting Suharto's complicity to Genosida '65.⁴⁵

Conversely, Leksana and Subekti proposed that social silence can be an expression of individual agency, and advocate for refocusing studies on the contexts and reasons around the silence to understand more of the complexities of post-conflict societies.⁴⁶ Furthermore, Leksana continued to explore how silence is also used as a survival or navigating tool by survivors and their families that goes beyond expression of trauma, in a way that silence enables them to continue living within their local context amidst the constructed taboos surrounding Genosida '65.⁴⁷

Despite the centrality of "taboo" in works about Genosida '65 memory, the specific concept of taboo has only been mentioned in passing without a deeper contextualised analysis. Leksana and Subekti, in their work exploring intergenerational transmission of memory of 1965 violence, mentioned how the culture of impunity creates taboo around the memory of the 1965 violence which further hinders discussion around the topic. Moreover, Eickhoff's 2017 study on Genosida '65 sites in Semarang found that acts of violence have attained a "taboo status" in Indonesian society, especially at the local level, making it difficult to trace and access relevant documents and archival materials.⁴⁸ As a response, spectral and haunting stories are used by Indonesians to bypass taboo surrounding the memory of Genosida '65 as explored by Leong.⁴⁹

⁴⁴ *Supersemar* stands for "*Surat Perintah Sebelas Maret*" or "the Letter of Instructions of 11th March" which was a document signed by president Sukarno on 11 March 1966 that gave mandate to Suharto as the TNI army lieutenant general to do everything in his power to "do whatever it takes" to manage order and governmental stability.

⁴⁵ Eddyono, 'The Shift in the Regime of Silence', 7.

⁴⁶ Leksana and Subekti, 'Remembering through Fragmented Narratives'.

⁴⁷ Leksana, *Memory Culture of the Anti-Leftist Violence in Indonesia*, 218.

⁴⁸ Eickhoff et al., 'The Memory Landscapes of "1965" in Semarang', 531.

⁴⁹ Leong, 'Invisible Threads Linking Phantasmal Landscapes in Java'; Leong, 'Keepers of the Grave'.

With how much sociality and locality is tied to a site, in the context of Genosida '65, one would need to dedicate a space for themes of spirituality to decode and comprehend an often-overlooked layer to memory sites. Missing the significance of such themes would render analysis or research on narratives of violence or the remnants of Genosida '65 hollow or disconnected as, even the semantics, phenomenon of haunting of unresolved stories of human rights abuses still linger within the current political space in Indonesia.⁵⁰

As of the writing of this thesis, the taboo surrounding *Genosida '65* memory appears to be an established reality, but further studies, such as one of how Indonesian society respond or navigate in the context of this taboo, would significantly contribute to the study of post-conflict, as Leksana and Eickhoff suggested. Additionally, understanding the varying degree of taboo that exist within different contexts could aid in local or community-level healing and reconciliation.

Many scholar also noted the perpetuity of silence, despite efforts to break through state-imposed silences on *Genosida '65*.⁵¹ Wieringa and Katjasungkana highlights that such silence and its perpetuity extend beyond the Indonesian state and society to the international human rights community, where the international community choose to be complicit in maintaining silence on as the Indonesian "hidden genocide".⁵² Narwaya describes a culture of silence (*kultur kebisuan*) that is being upheld by larger parts of the Indonesian society, in which they deliberately to opt to be *diam* (quiet, still) so as to not touch or avoid bringing up past pain.⁵³ This aversion towards the past with the argument as

⁵⁰ Leong, 'Invisible Threads Linking Phantasmal Landscapes in Java'; Leong, 'Keepers of the Grave'; Strassler, 'Fragments of Memory'.

⁵¹ Eickhoff et al., 'The Memory Landscapes of "1965" in Semarang'; Narwaya, *Kuasa Stigma Dan Represi Ingatan*; Dirgantoro, 'From Silence to Speech'; Leksana, 'Postmemory, Silence, and Trauma in Family Narratives'; Pamungkas, 'The Generation That Breaks the Silence'; Kusumaningrum et al., 'Sites of Violence, Sites of Peace, Sites of Justice', 313.

⁵² Wieringa and Katjasungkana, *Propaganda and the Genocide in Indonesia*, 167.

⁵³ Narwaya, *Kuasa Stigma Dan Represi Ingatan*; *SENYAP - The Look of Silence*.

not to “bring up past pain” is a common theme evident in the perpetrators’s testimonies in Oppenheimer’s *Act of Killing* and Tempo’s special edition covering *Genosida ’65* from 2014.⁵⁴

The logic behind this aversion towards the past could benefit from further sociological analysis of the taboo culture surrounding *Genosida ’65* memory and communism in Indonesia. Former president B.J. Habibie, successor of Suharto, had specifically mentioned how the act of opening up or addressing the taboos, in the context of past violence, is part of the new democratic regime of Reformasi.⁵⁵

Leksana’s analysis on approaching the study of silence within the context of genocide emphasised the importance of viewing silence not just as the absence of narrative, but as its own language. She uses the term “embedded memory” to describe how memories are ingrained or situated within specific local contexts or environment.⁵⁶ As such, this perspective reveals that society’s ways of remembering and recollection of violent events is not isolated or abstract, rather deeply intertwined with the particular social and geographical settings where they occurred, continuing into the aftermath.

Remembering

Remembering has been offered as a counter-propaganda tool by Wieringa and Katjasungkana. Additionally, Kusumaningrum posited that in its social dimension, remembering bridges the connection of memory transmission.⁵⁷ From her project, remembering through the Yogyakarta walking tour of sites of historic violence between university students and women survivors of the genocide also invokes a sense of empathy

⁵⁴ SENYAP - *The Look of Silence*; Tempo, *Pengakuan Algojo 1965: Investigasi Tempo Perihal Pembantaian 1965*.

⁵⁵ Budiawan, ‘When Memory Challenges History’, 39.

⁵⁶ Leksana, *Memory Culture of the Anti-Leftist Violence in Indonesia*, 23; Leksana, 216.

⁵⁷ Kusumaningrum et al., ‘Sites of Violence, Sites of Peace, Sites of Justice’.

and solidarity from the younger generation to those persecuted by *Genosida '65* and its prevailing remnants of systemic violence, challenging the dominant perspective Indonesian society has over communists, or those who are deemed as such. Such understanding supplements Leksana and Subekti's work by illustrating how remembering aids the intergenerational transmission of memory that extends beyond the family to broader social spaces outside.⁵⁸

Moreover, Budianta and Tiwon briefly discussed how remembering counters the politics of forgetting mentioned by Narwaya, stressing that remembering can occur independently from its sociality without forcing the need for one to verbalise.⁵⁹ Through this understanding, they underscored the personal and accessible nature of remembering.

Aside from countering propaganda and politics of forgetting, remembering can also reclaim collective memory by reimagining temporality through shifting the starting point or point zero of *Orde Baru* history. Wardaya suggested that remembering and centralising *Genosida '65* killings that started in early October 1965, rather than centralising the generals kidnapping in late September, can reshape the dominant historical narrative.⁶⁰ He pointed out that the temporal placement of the prevailing national holiday "*Hari Kesaktian Pancasila*", which supposedly commemorates how Pancasila triumphs over communists/PKI (which the metanarrative deems to be anti-nationalist), in late September reinforces the state-endorsed metanarrative. The lack of state initiative or desire to preserve any memory of *Genosida '65* highlights the need for memory work in Indonesia.⁶¹

⁵⁸ Leksana and Subekti, 'Remembering through Fragmented Narratives'.

⁵⁹ Budianta and Tiwon, *Trajectories of Memory*.

⁶⁰ Wardaya, 'Menembus Politik Ingatan'.

⁶¹ Wieringa and Katjasungkana, *Propaganda and the Genocide in Indonesia*, 164.

To summarise, a peek into the existing literature on the collective memory of *Genosida '65* reveals complex interplay between the recurring themes of hegemonic memory control by the military, silence, and remembering. This literature has attempted to lay down the foundation for understanding the ongoing impact of *Genosida '65* to Indonesian memory culture and the importance of reclaiming the collective memory in the hope to set the stage for the deeper exploration of the state of *Genosida '65* collective memory.

Firstly, scholars have explored ways in which hegemonic control of the *Genosida '65* collective memory is practiced by the Indonesian military. This includes specifically the replacement of memory, as opposed to destruction, which affects the memory of communism ideology as well as the Sukarno-Suharto regime transition. As well as through propaganda which manipulates the Indonesian society's emotions and exploit and exacerbate the anti-communist sentiments that have existed prior to the genocide.

Secondly, silence has been brought up by scholars as a tool by the *Orde Baru* military state, which is utilised to suppress oppositions, as well as alternative accounts, among other uses. However, silence have also been explored beyond the absence of narrative to a navigational and survival tool for the Indonesian society to cope in the post-conflict context. In a similar vein, the taboo surrounding *Genosida '65* collective memory, fuels the perpetuity of silence, specifically *Orde Baru* silence culture which stems from the fear of bringing up past pain. Although central, the aspect of taboo seems to be understudied. Thus, further research on the topic, particularly on how Indonesia society respond and navigate taboo in doing memory work for *Orde Baru* violence could contribute to understanding the larger aversion of bringing up the past in Indonesian politics.

Lastly, there are potential for the act or process remembering to be developed into a framework that can contribute into the larger quest of Indonesian memory work. Scholars have proposed the potential held remembering as a counter to propaganda and politics of forgetting, bridging intergenerational transmission of memory, and facilitating solidarity and empathy. Even larger, there is a potential for remembering, in its independent aspect beyond the social, to be utilised to reclaim collective memory through the reimagination of temporal placement.

Conceptual Framework

This chapter outlines the conceptual framework guiding this thesis by establishing key theories and concepts laid out by the recent works highlighted in the literature review. In addition to the three conceptual themes found from the previous chapter, I will also be introducing keywords to further contextualise the discussion to *Genosida '65* and provide the conceptual underpinnings of the research.

Indonesian Left/Communism

Indonesia's independence, as said by founding father Sukarno, is one of the left revolution, noting that the Indonesian generation of revolutionary anti-colonial fighters who fought in guerrilla wars are part of the initially common "leftists".⁶² However, through the killing campaigns of Genosida '65 in which the military targeted PKI and its sympathisers, with vague categorising, the Orde Baru regime rendered all that is opposition to the government is against the founding ideology of Pancasila, anti-nationalist, are all communists. From such dominant perspective, they did not discern between communism and the broader category of the "Left".

Collective Memory

Collective memory is not a static object, nor a singular "truth". Rather it is a phenomenon, historical process affected by ceaseless unearthing of the past, with its dynamic and immaterial quality. Moreover, collective memory gains a form of object permanence when seen as a snapshot taken of the incessant process of many different perceptions and narratives of particular past events. It helps seeing collective memory as an

⁶² Supriatma, 'Kata Pengantar: G30S, PKI, Dan Pembunuhan Massal', 4.

open stream of different individual narratives of a particular event of the past in which the public have access, in the form of contributing to and observing.

Adopting from Eickhoff and Wardaya's works, collective memory also refers to how narratives in dynamically connecting individuals temporally and spatially to each other. Accordingly, a collective memory that is threatened is one in which it loses its patent "collective" quality that primarily happens when an entity attempts to gain singular control over it in a way that access to it is limited, if not impossible. Akin to privatising a beach for a resort in a way that disallow local people to enter the beach. When such phenomenon happens, I refer to it as collective memory hegemony.

Reclaiming collective memory is a way in which people can respond to collective memory hegemony. Among others, a primary motivation behind reclaiming collective memory comes from how collective memory is deeply tied to identity and nationhood, hence if it is chained under hegemony, then a young country's nationhood would be dictated by the hegemony rather than defined by its diverse society. In this thesis, I posit that reclaiming collective memory can be done through remembering.

Silence

Silence is a powerful tool in memory politics, more than just being a marker for absence of narrative. In this research, silence has two potentials as a tool: for suppression, and for resistance and survival. In the context of collective memory hegemony, silence would follow the former in the form of suppressing and/or repressing attempts to reclaim collective memory or challenge the singular narrative hegemony. As a tool for resistance, silence is used deliberately to reclaim agency by survivors when opting to omit or to not verbalise their narratives.

“Kebenaran”⁶³

In his seminal work, Wiredu introduced the concept of truth as opinions, advocating for the cultivation of "open-mindedness" and fostering spaces for discussions surrounding these truths.⁶⁴ However, the *Orde Baru* regime starkly opposes the idea as it managed to enshrine the concept of absolute truth as a crucial weapon in its authoritarian regime. The G30S metanarrative was created and utilised, not merely as a dominant narrative, but as an absolute truth. The subsequent genocide, which unfolds in the metanarrative's wake (beyond the film itself), exemplifies Wiredu's concern about the potential for violent fanaticism when absolute truth is rigidly adhered to.

I firmly contend that such unwavering absolutism regarding truth not only dehumanises the very essence of truth but also provides fertile ground for violent fanaticism to thrive. Absolute truth acts as a monopolistic brute force, moving outside of its own body in dictating what can be deemed as truth and, in turn, becomes a potent tool for authoritarian regimes to suppress public discourse and discussions. Moreover, absolute truth paves the way for the robotic memorization of historical events, similar if not the same to the Freire banking concept of education, divorcing the memory of violence from its intrinsic human qualities. In response, my approach aligns with Wiredu's spirit, seeking to humanise the conception of truth as an extension of human experience, rather than succumbing to fatalistic absolutism.

Practically, *kebenaran* is often synonymous with the English term "truth." However, its roots in the foundational word "*benar*", encapsulating notions of "correct" or "right," bestow upon *kebenaran* an unwavering assertion of correctness, subtly acknowledging the

⁶³ This section is derived from: Malahayati, 2024

⁶⁴ Wiredu, 'Truth as Opinion'.

existence of its counterpart, though not with a judgement that they are not correct. A distinct sense of virtue permeates the very essence of the *kebenaran*, it does not enforce singularity through its existence.

In contrast to the English "truth," *kebenaran* unfolds as more than a factual statement—it carries a deeper implication of humanness and subjectivity. As I encounter *kebenaran*, the inclination is towards perceiving truth as a personal narrative, understanding that it weaves varied meanings for different individuals. In this essence, *kebenaran* transcends the clinical objectivity often tethered to the term "truth," embracing the multifaceted nature of human experience and perspective.

Keluarga Korban

As discussed earlier, the label "*keluarga korban*" is not only inherent but also steadfast, exerting a pervasive influence that eclipses other identifiers within the realm of activism. Whether a *keluarga korban* is actively involved in political movements, participating in protests, or refraining from such engagements, the persisting memory of their family's victimhood remains a constant. Even in instances of deep involvement in activism, the "activist" label does not supersede the overarching identity of "*keluarga korban*." Consequently, the legitimacy, validity, and weight of their opinions on matters related to human rights or historical instances of violence are inherently intertwined with their *keluarga korban* identity.

Research Questions

1. What is the purpose of the G30S metanarrative of Suharto's Orde Baru?
2. How can the collective memory hegemony over Genosida '65 be contested in the public space?

3. What role does community play in preserving collective memory?

Methodology

This thesis research is conducted through the anthropological approach of ethnography, specifically militant ethnography, a methodological approach pioneered by Juris⁶⁵ that intentionally blurs the boundary between deliberate engagement with the advocacy work and research. Such method is indispensable in elucidating my positionality within this complex landscape as one of the many *keluarga korban* of Orde Baru political violence. Practitioners of ethnography within the sphere of resistance recognize the pivotal role that activist networks play, serving as the beating heart that navigates the affective regime integral to understanding the intricacies of human experience. Amidst the intricate entanglements of these networks, it is imperative to approach ethnography not as a quest for definitive answers but with an open and observant mind, paying attention to the things often overlooked. The study of human nuances, often dismissed but inherently valuable, requires an appreciation for the complexity, whimsy, and spontaneity of behaviour. Two practical methods I adopted are archival research and ethnographic fieldwork.

Foremost, I conducted archival research through the online archive of “*Perpustakaan Online Genosida 1965*” by Andreas Iswinarto.⁶⁶ Later on, I conducted fieldworks within three provinces of the Java Island: Yogyakarta, East Java, and Jakarta.

Chapter one explores the G30S metanarrative through ethnography conducted of a visit to the national sites located in the fourteen-point-six-hectare complex of *Monumen Pancasila Sakti*, in Lubang Buaya, East Jakarta. The state-built complex is the epicentre and, arguably heart, of the preservation and immortalisation effort of the G30S metanarrative in Indonesia. It consists of nine separate sites, not including various displays of vehicles among

⁶⁵ Juris, ‘Introduction: The Cultural Logic of Networking’.

⁶⁶ ‘Perpustakaan Online Genosida 1965-1966’.

others. The museums combined have over fifty dioramas, some life-sized, of selected events from 1945 until 1974 mostly depicting violence or chaos by PKI and its affiliates.

Chapter two on counter-narratives is done through ethnographic tools which complement my positionality within the research as a *keluarga korban* with a pre-existing intimate relationship with the Genosida '65 community. The ethnographic approach is done with the Indonesian concept of "*napak tilas*" which refers to the act of walking through specific paths or areas to revisit memory. The second chapter deals with spatial memory and spirituality, thus I visited of the genocide mass graves (*kuburan massal*) or execution sites in Yogyakarta and the surrounding Central Java. As the mass graves are not well-known outside of its locality, nonofficially acknowledged by the state, the locations visited are chosen through an informal "tour" guidance from a colleague whose contact was acquired through my personal connection with Genosida '65 community familiar with the areas. Given my personal background that relates to Central Java, I chose to conduct my fieldwork in Yogyakarta and its surrounding villages. This familiarity with the culture and people informed my decision to focus on this region. Outside of personal communication, my first encounter of the locations of Genosida '65 mass graves came from Tempo's 2013 special edition, "Pengakuan Algojo 1965".⁶⁷

Chapter three is an ethnographic analysis of the online archive "*Perpustakaan Online Genosida '65*" to which I conducted several interviews with an archivist, some contributors, and the creator, Andreas Iswinarto, himself. Additionally, I interacted with the online archive regularly over the span of three months. The archival research was conducted in late

⁶⁷ Tempo, *Pengakuan Algojo 1965: Investigasi Tempo Perihal Pembantaian 1965*.

2023 and was previously submitted for a master's course I was enrolled in by Prof. Patricia Spyer titled "Archive, Memory, History" in IHEID.

Books or specific official documentations surrounding the transition of Sukarno's regime to Orde Baru, Genosida '65, and PKI are difficult to attain publicly due to the former regime's relationship with socialism and the aforementioned TAP MPRS No.

XXV/MPRS/1966, as such I gathered relevant materials from the "*Perpustakaan Online Genosida '65*", interpersonal communication with the Genosida '65 community, and my family's personal book collection which used to be part of our leftist bookstore.

Chapter 1 : The G30S Metanarrative

In the dark hours of 30 September 1965, seven high-ranking TNI generals were abducted from the sanctity of their homes by a group of armed men. Those who resisted met a tragic end, gunned down before the eyes of their families. Subsequently, the TNI victims, whether alive or lifeless, were transported to a base in Lubang Buaya, East Jakarta. There, a harrowing ordeal unfolded as the kidnapped bodies were subjected to unspeakable acts—genital mutilation, cigarette burns, razor cuts, and eyes gouging. The torture took place with not only the initial kidnapers, but also a cultish group, including topless women, participating in a ritualistic torture. On that faithful day, Lubang Buaya base which serves as a training ground for the largest communist women's organisation, Gerwani, became a gruesome site of brutality. The TNI generals were ultimately buried, some still breathing, into a well. The subsequent week revealed the shocking news that the armed kidnapers were part of TNI that were affiliated with the then-dominant political party, the PKI.

This torture-focused and PKI-centric metanarrative, commonly referred to as "G30S/PKI" in historical accounts, played a pivotal role in facilitating the hegemony of Indonesian Genosida '65 collective memory.

Echoing the introduction, the semantic of G30S/PKI itself is part of the main propaganda campaign used throughout the Orde Baru regime. G30S stands for "*Gerakan 30 September*" (30th September Movement) referring to the kidnapping of the army generals, is crucially linked with a forward slash "PKI" (The Indonesian Communist Party). There have been debates on the historical accuracy surrounding the kidnappings. The dominant Orde Baru state-endorsed narrative, which we refer to the G30S metanarrative, dictates that the kidnappings are part of an abortive coup attempt by PKI themselves to replace Sukarno. On the other side, many historical analysts have contested this dominant claim by referring to

the G30S event as an internal conflict within the TNI in which the individual kidnappers' respective affiliation to the PKI not playing a central role to the operation. The linkage of "G30S/PKI" is a deliberate attempt by TNI to remind the society that PKI is the sole actor that is responsible for the G30S kidnapping and its horrors, as is continuously claimed well into the Reformasi era through the ceaseless book banning which include historical textbook that uses the term "G30S" without the "/PKI" at its end.⁶⁸

The G30S metanarrative found its immortality in an almost four-hour "documentary" released in 1984. Commissioned by Suharto himself, the film titled "*Pengkhianatan G30S/PKI*"⁶⁹ became Indonesia's first domestically commercialised film. Screened annually on October 1st, a nationally designated day supposedly to commemorate the kidnappings and the Indonesian Pancasila ideology over communism, the film perpetuated anti-communist propaganda. With explicit and uncensored portrayals of the aforementioned torture, the film became mandatory viewing for schoolchildren, starting from primary school, every year until the end of the Orde Baru regime in 1998.⁷⁰ The film served as a form of imposed memory by the state, reinforcing the metanarrative crafted by the regime. As the film was released nearly two decades after the genocide, the film itself did not act retroactively as a catalyst for the 1965 events, but rather subsequently to sustain and amplify the violent anti-communist sentiment by immortalising the G30S metanarrative.

In understanding Genosida '65 collective memory, we need to address the G30S metanarrative that dominates discussion of PKI in Indonesia as well as the transition from Orde Lama to Orde Baru. In this chapter, I shall attempt to address the purpose of collective memory hegemony held by G30S metanarrative in the advent of Suharto's Orde Baru

⁶⁸ Siregar, 'Menggugat Pelarangan Buku'; Yusuf et al., 'Sejarah Pelarangan Buku di Indonesia'.

⁶⁹ In English: Treachery of *G30S/PKI*.

⁷⁰ Ticoalu, *Tak Ada Penyiksaan Terhadap 6 Jenderal: Wawancara Dengan DR. Liaw Yan Siang*, 7.

regime which is marked by Genosida '65. This chapter includes my fieldwork on the *Monumen Pancasila Sakti* complex, an official site of TNI's history, which I address as the nexus of the G30S metanarrative to gain a deeper insight to what space the metanarrative takes in Indonesian history according to the most powerful entity of the time, the TNI.

1.1. TNI and its many duties

Indonesian 'official' history, which feeds to the collective memory of the genocide, is controlled by the military.⁷¹ Eddyono describes how Suharto's military Orde Baru specifically controlled public memory is typical of an authoritarian regime.⁷² Thus, the G30S metanarrative reflects the position of power TNI held throughout the Orde Baru dictatorship.

The G30S metanarrative propagated by the TNI, justifying their involvement as a response to pre-existing tensions, has been debunked by archival declassifications and counternarrative research. Particularly Leksana's study on the declassification of key archives from East Java's kodam (military command) revealed clear structural instructions from central military authorities down to non-military leaders involved in kidnappings, torture, and killings.⁷³ Moreover, inconsistencies present in the *visum et repertum* of the kidnapped generals, non-transparency, and lack of encouragement for further critical historical studies surrounding G30S and PKI further questions the legitimacy of the military's G30S metanarrative, which is attempting to maintain hegemony over collective memory, as they did in Orde Baru. The intention is not to assign more accountability to one party over the other, but rather to recognise the disproportionate power the TNI holds with their

⁷¹ McGregor, *History in Uniform*; Munir, 'The Future of the Civil-Military Relationship in Indonesia'; Eddyono, 'The Shift in the Regime of Silence'; Eickhoff et al., 'The Memory Landscapes of "1965" in Semarang'.

⁷² Robinson, 'The Killing Season'; Eddyono, 'The Shift in the Regime of Silence', 3.

⁷³ Leksana.

heightened power during the Orde Baru regime over Indonesia's collective memory and particularly regarding Genosida '65.

Early writings on Orde Baru often stress the importance of history-writing that acknowledges the power grip the military has over the memory.⁷⁴

A crucial aspect of understanding this period is examining the political dynamics and doctrines that facilitated the TNI's hegemony over Genosida '65 collective memory. Key among these is the Sukarno-PKI-TNI relationships and the '*dwifungsi*' (dual function) doctrine implemented by Suharto, which intertwined the military's role in both security and politics.

The triangle relationship indicates the three main political powers in newly independent Orde Lama Indonesia: Sukarno, the republic's first President; PKI, the largest non-ruling communist political party in the world; and TNI, the Indonesian national military. Within the triangle, Sukarno acted as a stabiliser between the two latter who were competing in influence on Indonesian politics. As such, one of the many competitions being TNI advocating for military involvement in politics, while PKI opposing it.⁷⁵ Conflicts between the TNI and PKI had been brewing for a while, setting the stage for the transition to Orde Baru.⁷⁶ PKI's power at the time could be attributed to how Indonesian national liberation was branded as leftist by the with how Dutch colonial power as it was an independence movement, as well as Sukarno's reiteration on how Indonesia's revolution is a left-wing revolution. Sukarno himself had suggested and was supported by 1959-1965 general

⁷⁴ Munir, 'The Future of the Civil-Military Relationship in Indonesia', 78; Leksana, 'Conclusion', 220; McGregor, *History in Uniform*; Curaming, 'The Contrasting Calculus of Power in Sejarah Nasional Indonesia (SNI) and the Tadhana Project', 364.

⁷⁵ Rinakit, 'Military during the Pre-Reform Period', 23.

⁷⁶ Hardoyo, 'The Future of the Left in Indonesia', 157.

meetings of MPR(S)⁷⁷ to develop Indonesia's ideology as "socialism *a la* Indonesia" that is interpreted as religious socialism.⁷⁸

Aside from that, the TNI, as part of the Indonesian National Armed Forces (ABRI), possessed the distinctive "*dwifungsi*" doctrine throughout Orde Baru, granting it dual functions as a security force and political authority. This unique characteristic motivated the military to be more involved and garner support from the local people, often through civic action programs which continued well into Reformasi.

Suharto took a step further by tacitly attributing the *dwifungsi* function as one the primary character of his regime that deifies 'development'. Those opposing the *dwifungsi* function were labeled anti-development, and therefore anti-Pancasila.⁷⁹ Relying on the *dwifungsi* function, the TNI and police forces were paired under a new entity name of ABRI (*Angkatan Bersenjata Republik Indonesia/ The Indonesian Republic Armed Force*) became the political tool of Suharto's *Orde Baru*.⁸⁰ In his book with Caldwell, Utrecht criticised this replacement of civil functionaries by the military through *dwifungsi*, which he said to result in "severe harm" to the state administration as the military occupied top posts in the beginning of the *Orde Baru* regime.⁸¹

Unfortunately, this "octopus institution", as Munir called it, where the TNI became the "planner, executor, and supervisor of state coordination," remains observable in Reformasi era Indonesia.⁸² Munir's work at the dawn of Reformasi speaks on the need for a

⁷⁷ People's Consultative Assembly.

⁷⁸ Hardoyo, 'The Future of the Left in Indonesia', 152.

⁷⁹ Rinakit, 'Military during the Pre-Reform Period', 27.

⁸⁰ Rinakit, 'Towards the New Paradigm', 61; Munir, 'The Future of the Civil-Military Relationship in Indonesia', 72.

⁸¹ Caldwell and Utrecht, *Sejarah alternatif Indonesia*, 163.

⁸² Munir, 'The Future of the Civil-Military Relationship in Indonesia'.

democratic formulation of civil-military relationships, clearly defining that the military cannot hold an absolute independent force position, a concern still relevant today.

Currently following the 2024 presidential election result of Prabowo, the TNI law (UU TNI) is at the process of revision which would include the expansion of TNI's mandate within civic spaces, with many expressing concerns that the revisions show signs of the return of the *dwifungsi* role to the military.⁸³ In response, TNI Commander General Agus Subiyanto, in a self-contradicting manner, stated that as of now TNI is already "*multifungsi*" (multifunction), referring to an example of his TNI colleagues teaching in schools in Papua, at the same breath stating that the worry for *dwifungsi* ABRI revival is exaggerated.⁸⁴

As the foundation of its justification, the G30S metanarrative, has had its legitimacy ruptured by societies and scholars in Indonesia and abroad. Despite this, with the help of the Indonesian state, TNI still frantically attempts to sustain the legitimacy with considerably less power in the post-Orde Baru regime. The metanarrative still prevails and dominates in the memory landscape of most Indonesian society.

This persistence is evident through the preservation of state-made public sites such as the Monumen Pancasila Sakti complex, a 14.6-hectare site hosting various memorials, including the infamous *Museum Pengkhianatan PKI (Komunis)*⁸⁵ at Lubang Buaya, East Jakarta. Roosa, in "Pretext of Mass Murders," describes how Lubang Buaya, which holds the Monumen Pancasila Sakti complex, became a holy site for Suharto's claimed state religion, anti-communism.⁸⁶ The site was initially built in 1973 by the Suharto government

⁸³ Imparsial, 'RUU TNI Akan Mengembalikan DwiFungsi ABRI Dan Mengancam Demokrasi'; Prasetyo, 'DPR Dikabarkan Akan Godok Lagi Revisi UU TNI, Imparsial Khawatir Dwifungsi ABRI Kembali'.

⁸⁴ CNN Indonesia, 'Panglima soal RUU TNI'; VIDEO; Kompas Cyber Media, 'Soal Isu Dwifungsi ABRI di RUU TNI, Panglima'.

⁸⁵ In English: Museum of the PKI (Communists) Treachery

⁸⁶ Roosa, *Pretext for Mass Murder*, 9.

intentionally to depict violence and torture by the PKI and 'communists' against the TNI.⁸⁷

Temporally, the metanarrative is also preserved through the aforementioned annual commemoration on the 1st October "*Hari Kebangkitan Pancasila*".

The prevalence of the G30S metanarrative can also be seen through reigning president Joko 'Jokowi' Widodo's attendance at a public viewing of the aforementioned *Pengkhianatan G30S/PKI* propaganda film with the TNI Commander General Gatot Nurmantyo in the Military Resort Command (*Korem*) in Bogor, West Java in 2017.⁸⁸ Gatot Nurmantyo commanded the military to rewatch the film to remember the history of the nation. The viewing of the gory film was open to the public and was attended by primary school children as young as 12 years old. Through his unspoken support of Gatot Nurmantyo's command, Jokowi had symbolically revived the legitimacy of the movie.

The contrast between the preservation of the state-made sites endorsing the G30S metanarrative and PKI/communist caricature and Genosida '65 is jarring. The *Monumen Pancasila Sakti* complex, built to commemorate the kidnappings and death of the TNI generals, stands vast and saturated. While the non-existent official memorial site for Genosida '65, let alone memorial site for the hundreds of thousands Indonesians tortured, massacred, or disappeared, pales.⁸⁹

1.2. Visiting the crocodiles' den (Lubang Buaya)

I visited Lubang Buaya on a Monday for the first time in my life as part of this fieldwork, hoping that the *Monumen Pancasila Sakti* complex would not be too crowded.

My father came along, as he had never previously visited the place and is curious of its

⁸⁷ Leksana and Subekti, 'Remembering through Fragmented Narratives', 468.

⁸⁸ Hindarto, 'Jokowi Dan Panglima TNI Nobar Film G30S/PKI'.

⁸⁹ Wieringa and Katjasungkana, *Propaganda and the Genocide in Indonesia*, 164; Leksana, *Memory Culture of the Anti-Leftist Violence in Indonesia*.

interiors. Entering the palatial complex, we were given a small booklet with a map of the complex, guiding us on our foot throughout the day with its inclusive tour guide-like narration of the museums and their dioramas, sites, and the displays scattered around the complex.⁹⁰ The narration for the dioramas seem to construct the present-day version of the notorious G30S metanarrative.

The sensation of entering the Monumen Pancasila Sakti complex which surrounds you completely with the G30S metanarrative, makes me think of the time immediately after the G30S kidnappings when all non-military newspapers were censored, and all you know was the PKI's complicity to the kidnappings of TNI generals.⁹¹

Reading the updated G30S metanarrative in the booklet, although refraining from specific mentions of the kidnapped generals' torture, and observing the complex surroundings, you can still see how the original dramatized G30S metanarrative version with the ritualistic torture is the foundation of which the complex is built upon, hence the told violence is embedded spatially. Although the booklet offered omitted false parts of the kidnapped generals' torture specificity, I still refer to the updated G30S narrative as a metanarrative. This is because the metanarrative remains a remnant of Orde Baru's militaristic legitimacy, as well as it still denies space for contestation in terms of its *kebenaran*; the G30S metanarrative offered throughout the complex seemed to lack analysis or citation to any official documents, nor any form of non-TNI analysis. To emphasise, the lack of proper analysis would not be a problem if it were offered as just a narrative, but this G30S metanarrative originated from the military state, and is still being

⁹⁰ Monumen Pancasila Sakti, 'Buku Panduan: Monumen Pancasila Sakti'. There are separate Bahasa Indonesia and English booklets. I acquired the Bahasa Indonesia version, presumably the original version, thus the keywords and quotations from the booklet are my personal translation.

⁹¹ Ticoalu, *Tak Ada Penyiksaan Terhadap 6 Jenderal: Wawancara Dengan DR. Liaw Yan Siang*, 47; Supriatma, 'Kata Pengantar: G30S, PKI, Dan Pembunuhan Massal', 3.

sustained and subtly promoted by the government, as the sole *kebenaran*, which contradicts and appropriates the concept itself. In other words, it is still seeking hegemony over the Orde Baru collective memory.

While the abductions and murders of TNI generals entailed by the metanarrative occurred, the described ritualistic torture has been debunked by revisiting the generals' autopsy reports or *visum et repertum*.⁹² However, dismantling such deeply ingrained indoctrination remains a protracted and challenging endeavour, especially considering the Orde Baru regime's persistence to 1998.

Through cross-checking the official copy of the *visum et repertum* and the autopsy reports embedded in the museum, as well as the booklet, I noticed a handful of inconsistencies.

Based on the booklet, these inconsistencies were evident in the narratives of Brigadier General (*Brigjen*) D.I. Panjaitan and Lieutenant General M.T. Harjono. The metanarrative states that the kidnappers shot Brigjen D.I. Panjaitan's body after he was already fatally shot in the head.⁹³ Despite this, the *visum et repertum* clearly states that there are only three bullet wounds that entered his body, all of which are located on his head.⁹⁴

In M.T. Harjono's case, the metanarrative claims that Bungkus laid the shot that finally killed M.T. Harjono.⁹⁵ However, the *visum et repertum* found no bullet wounds, only

⁹² See Ticoalu, *Tak Ada Penyiksaan Terhadap 6 Jenderal: Wawancara Dengan DR. Liaw Yan Siang*, in which he interviewed Dr. Liaw Yan Siang, one of the only remaining two people who were responsible for the autopsy reports (*visum et repertum*) of the kidnapped generals which are used for persecuting the culprits of the kidnappings in the Mahmilub (Mahkamah Militer Luar Blasa/Extraordinary Military Court). Within it, he also attached the official copy of each of the generals' *visum et repertum* he received from political scientist Professor Emeritus Benedict Anderson who previously worked on the "Cornell Paper".

⁹³ Monumen Pancasila Sakti, 'Buku Panduan: Monumen Pancasila Sakti', 34.

⁹⁴ Ticoalu, *Tak Ada Penyiksaan Terhadap 6 Jenderal: Wawancara Dengan DR. Liaw Yan Siang*, 74.

⁹⁵ Monumen Pancasila Sakti, 'Buku Panduan: Monumen Pancasila Sakti', 32.

stabbing and open wounds.⁹⁶ These inconsistencies, in addition to the lack of reference documents, scientific studies, and the TAP MPRS No. XXV/MPRS/1966 alongside book bans, further question the legitimacy of the current G30S metanarrative.

Outside of the booklet, the dioramas, arguably the most famous feature of the complex, powerfully act as propaganda tools. They are most prominently displayed in the "Torture House" and the two museums: *Museum Pengkhianatan PKI (Komunis)*, which holds dioramas of PKI's history of violence, and Museum Paseban, which holds several real size dioramas and the rooms containing the clothes of the kidnapped generals, among other exhibits.

Witnessing the dioramas first-hand invoked a strong affective response within myself, especially the real-size dioramas which encapsulate and surround my being. In this way, I use the dioramas to understand elementarily the affective regime which coloured the regime transition between Orde Lama and Orde Baru. Particularly, the "Torture House" with its real-size figures and lack of any glass barriers, in its own constructed space, creates an incredibly immersive experience as a witness to the kidnapped generals' torture. The Torture House is sized like a regular semi-open wooden house with a window on each of its three sides, creating the feeling of almost peeking in and limiting the lighting that enters the room, making it more sombre, personal, eery. It is impossible to fully take in the scene in its entirety simply by looking directly into one of the windows without peeking in, doing so made me feel as if the figures in my peripheral vision had come to life.

⁹⁶ Ticoalu, *Tak Ada Penyiksaan Terhadap 6 Jenderal: Wawancara Dengan DR. Liaw Yan Siang*, 65–66.

Figure 1.1. My father looking into the Torture House's window (Photo by author).

Figure 1.2. A look into the Torture House's window (Photo by author).

The Torture House is equipped with an endless looping audio narrating the story of the kidnapped generals who were still alive and were then tortured. Accompanied with a sombre violin instrumental in the background, the lengthy audio included incredibly vivid

sounds of multiple gunshots and haunting screaming. Such terrorising sounds felt eerily similar to the audio used in the propaganda movie.⁹⁷

⁹⁷ For those interested and willing, it is a good idea to inquire about the audio directly to the Museum's official Whatsapp chat: <https://wa.me/6281219120965>

Figure 1.3. Corridor inside the *Museum Pengkhianatan PKI (Komunis)* (Photo by author).

The museum dioramas also created an unsettling liminal feeling which was intensified by the empty corridors during our visit as can be seen in Figure 1.3. These

corridors, drab with low ceilings and faint yellow paint, lead visitors through the chronological diorama depicting PKI-related scenes in medium to large glass cases.

Figure 1.4. Corridor inside Museum Paseban, diorama #7 on lefthand side (Photo by author).

Figure 1.5. Diorama #7: the kidnapping of General A.H. Nasution (Photo by author).

For me, the most jarring diorama was the one located in the Museum Paseban, the second museum which entry is directly connected to the exit of *Museum Pengkhianatan PKI (Komunis)*. Diorama # 7 titled “The Kidnapping of General A.H. Nasution (1 October 1965)”⁹⁸, as can be seen in Figure 1.4 and Figure 1.5 depicted A.H. Nasution’s figure climbing the wall fencing his house to escape the kidnapers. Although the real-size character of diorama #7 is similar to that of the “Torture House”, diorama #7 is sealed within a glass barrier which is almost floor-to-ceiling in height, creating a fuller and unobstructed field of view to the scene.

⁹⁸ In Bahasa Indonesia: “*Penculikan Jenderal A.H. Nasution (1 Oktober 1965)*”.

The description of the Torture House diorama contained heavy dramatization, with the Gerwani members described as "dancing" and "laughing" during the torture sessions. In this way I posit that the dioramas' main goal is not to "acknowledge the tragedy that has struck in our country and was done by PKI"⁹⁹ under the name of history as it so claims in their introduction, rather the dioramas are created to fuel and sustain the caricature of PKI that is continued to be used as the campaign which invokes the same affective regime that enabled Genosida '65.

Notably, the only a select few of the museum dioramas are real-size, such as the ones depicting the kidnapping scenes of the generals. These real-size dioramas with their glass barricades create an immersive experience to the visitors as if they are direct witnesses to the scenes.

Another thing about the otherwise "complete" chronological diorama in the museum, is that there is a gap between 1965-1966 dioramas. The temporal gap is presented subtly and coyly, it can be observed by the absence of the depiction or mention of any form of violence (let alone execution) directed to PKI members and its sympathisers, between G30S (1 October 1965) to the end of 1966 (which only had 2 events mentioned in the year). The end of 1966 is marked by a diorama titled "The people of Jakarta welcomed the disbandment of PKI (12 March 1966)"¹⁰⁰ which narrative ended with the following sentences:

*"(...) Keputusan pembubaran PKI diumumkan melalui RRI pada pukul 06:00 WIB tanggal 12 Maret 1966. Keputusan ini **disambut hangat** oleh seluruh rakyat Indonesia.*

⁹⁹ Monumen Pancasila Sakti, 'Buku Panduan: Monumen Pancasila Sakti'.

¹⁰⁰ In Bahasa Indonesia: "*Rakyat Jakarta Menyambut Pembubaran PKI (12 Maret 1966)*"

*Massa rakyat Jakarta menyambutnya dengan membawa poster-poster sebagai ungkapan rasa gembira dan terima kasih.*¹⁰¹

If the date seems familiar, it is because the diorama refers to the day after the creation of the notorious *Supersemar*, the elusive document which grants Suharto the power to ban PKI officially and later validated the transfer of Sukarno's executive power to his would-be successor, Suharto.

Aside from the dioramas, there is also a powerful play of semantics and slogans throughout the complex. This includes not only within the dioramas-filled museums, but also in the signs and the booklet that governs my understanding of the current updated G30S metanarrative.

Foremost is how "PKI" is used interchangeably with "communists" as can be seen of how their biggest museum, *Museum Pengkhianatan PKI (Komunis)* puts "communists" as the explanatory brackets for "PKI". Such deliberate attempt shows TNI's refusal to frame PKI's status independently as a political party, nor communism independently as an ideology, simultaneously forcing the two to be interchangeable. Consequently, the image of PKI that is made equivalent to a vague communist ideology or other times as a vague organization endorsing violence for an underexplained communist ideology. This is especially due to PKI's ideology is not once discussed within the G30S metanarrative space, some brief mentions of PKI's ideology are only a reductive and accusatory take of the ideology being anti-nationalist. After all, the booklet states that PKI's ultimate goal is to replace Pancasila with communism, seen as inherently anti-Pancasila.¹⁰²

¹⁰¹ In English: "(...) The decision to disband the PKI was announced via RRI (The Indonesian National Radio) at 06:00 WIB on March 12 1966. This decision was **warmly welcomed** by all the Indonesian people. The masses of the people of Jakarta welcomed it by bringing posters as an **expression of joy and gratitude**." Emphasis added by author.

¹⁰² Monumen Pancasila Sakti, 'Buku Panduan: Monumen Pancasila Sakti', i.

Throughout the visit, the lack of explanation of what PKI even is creates a confusion as to who the people are and why so many people, specifically *buruh* (labor workers) and *petani* (farmers), support them. This possibly creates an image of PKI as solely a vague organisation, with no clear legality, that terrorises the country and endorse violence for the (also vague and underexplained) communist ideology.

The dioramas depict PKI-led revolutions as violent and cruel (*kejam*), promoting the perception of PKI members as inherently violent rather than examining the context and significance of their actions. For example, diorama #5 of *Museum Pengkhianatan PKI (Komunis)* titled “Events of the Social Revolution in Langkat (9 March 1946)”¹⁰³ in which PKI enacted a social revolution that killed the kings and their families, as well as looted their riches in Eastern Sumatera, which description does not include even a slight mention or implication of the possible socioeconomic tension between the elite monarchs and the local people.¹⁰⁴ Moreover, I find that within this example the Museum had made a bold choice choosing the term “revolution” and proceed to appropriate it in a manner that would paint PKI in an antagonistic light.

¹⁰³ In Bahasa Indonesia: “*Peristiwa Revolusi Sosial di Langkat (9 Maret 1946)*”

¹⁰⁴ Monumen Pancasila Sakti, ‘Buku Panduan: Monumen Pancasila Sakti’, 8.

Figure 1.6. Diorama #9 “Murder in Kawedanan Ngawen, Blora (20 September 1948)”¹⁰⁵
(Photo by author).

¹⁰⁵ In Bahasa Indonesia: “*Pembunuhan di Kawedanan Ngawen, Blora (20 September 1948)*”

Another example is a diorama #9 titled “Murder in Kawedanan Ngawen, Blora (20 September 1948)” which vividly describes the brutal execution of police personals by PKI forces, emphasizing on PKI’s cruelty. The diorama tells the story of the raid of the Ngawen, Blora District Police Headquarter which took twenty-four police personnel as hostages and how the communists executed the polices using two bamboo stalks held by two people to clamp to the neck of the people. After such description of the execution, in the diorama narrative it is written: “(...) *Ketika tawanan mengerang-erang kesakitan, pasukan PKI bersorak gembira (...)*.”¹⁰⁶

Furthermore, the maintained violent label of the PKI is evident throughout the complex's graphic and brutal depictions of the PKI, deliberate omissions of context and background to the PKI’s history in the museums, and characteristically militaristic anti-communist slogans.

¹⁰⁶ In English: “When the prisoners cried in pain, the PKI troops cheered happily (...).” Monumen Pancasila Sakti, ‘Buku Panduan: Monumen Pancasila Sakti’, 10.

Figure 1.7. A. H. Nasution's quote at *Gedung Pendopo* (pavilion) outdoor (Photo by author).

Figure 1.8. A. H. Nasution's quote in Museum Paseban (Photo by author).

A recurring quote by A.H. Nasution reads: "We have all been slandered and our brothers have been killed; we have been treated in this way, but do not hold grudges, faith in Allah SWT, faith in Him, strengthens us because He commands us all to have the obligation to uphold justice and truth." This quote is displayed prominently throughout the complex, both in exterior and interior spaces, as well as in the booklet's page right after the cover.

With that, we can see how the metanarrative's point of departure is that communist ideology, as interpreted by TNI, is one that is inherently anti-Pancasila¹⁰⁷ and hence anti-

¹⁰⁷ Pancasila, created as the nation's ideology, refers to the five (*panca*) principles (*sila*) to which Indonesia should be operating on. It was formulated through BPUPKI that consisted of nationalist and Islamist figures of Indonesia. Mohammad Yamin, Soepomo, and Sukarno, the first president, were the three people who suggested the core formulations of Pancasila. To reiterate from the earlier part of this thesis, the Indonesian revolution is an anti-colonial leftist revolution that centres *petani* and *buruh* and as communist and socialist

nationalist. This specifically touches on the caricature of PKI that is immoral and anti-religion, noting that the first principle of Pancasila is: "Belief in the one and only God."¹⁰⁸

To win over and solidify the G30S metanarrative, the military exploited the religious communities in Indonesia, leveraging the high value placed on religion. To oppose the PKI, the military employed a narrative that labelled the PKI as violent, immoral/perverse, and anti-religion. I adopt Wieringa and Katjasungkana's claim that the communism spectre in Indonesia is rendered through the G30S metanarrative as associated with atheism (interpreted as anti-theism), sexual perversion, and anti-nationalism.¹⁰⁹ As such, validating PKI caricature means that communists can be seen as "moral enemies" and can be dehumanized, hence Genosida '65 can be painted as a necessary step for the sake of ideological stability of the nation.

1.3. Justifying a genocide

Recalling the first research question of this thesis, this chapter attempted to examine the purpose of the G30S metanarrative which I find is to provide legitimacy for Genosida '65. In turn, the legitimacy to Genosida '65 extends to Suharto's rise to power and thus the legitimacy to Orde Baru's advent.¹¹⁰ Furthermore, the collective memory hegemony continuously pursued by G30S metanarrative through symbols such as Lubang Buaya complex and national holidays functions as a display of Orde Baru's power, which creates extra protection to the regime's legitimacy.

ideologies are part of leftist thoughts, Pancasila itself is influenced by such ideologies. That is why Pancasila is focused on the grassroots concepts such as "*kerakyatan*" (democracy) and "*keadilan sosial*" (social justice).

¹⁰⁸ In Bahasa Indonesia: "*Ketuhanan yang Maha Esa*."

¹⁰⁹ Wieringa and Katjasungkana, *Propaganda and the Genocide in Indonesia*.

¹¹⁰ Sebastian, 'Enframing Indonesian Concepts of National Security', 374; Roosa, *Pretext for Mass Murder*, 9; Munir, 'The Future of the Civil-Military Relationship in Indonesia', 71.

As a main memory site to the metanarrative, the Lubang Buaya complex plays a crucial role in upholding the PKI caricatures, particularly through its dioramas and slogans, which are the primary vehicles for propaganda within the affective regime. The updated G30S metanarrative, as perpetuated by the complex and promoted by the TNI, remains a metanarrative as it continues to assert itself as the appropriated version of "*kebenaran*" in the pursuit of sustaining collective memory hegemony.

Chapter 2: Genosida '65 on a Map

What happens to narratives that do not seek to be the singular truth or dominate others? What becomes of the stories that lack the power and influence enforced by the military since the Orde Baru?

Outside of the power struggle of the G30S metanarrative in its endless pursuit of maintaining collective memory hegemony, exist multitudes of individualised and communal memories of violence surrounding Genosida '65.

With the genocide creating a vaguely broad categorisation of PKI and communists as complicit or responsible to the kidnappings of the generals, millions of mass imprisonments without trials proliferated across the country, Sumatera, Java, Bali, Sulawesi, Nusa Tenggara islands.¹¹¹ Characteristic to a genocide, such political detainees were categorised into three groups (group A, group B, group C) based on their supposed involvement to the G30S kidnapping. Group A constitutes those who are directly involved and brought into “justice”, such as Dipa Nusa Aidit, the former president of PKI. Meanwhile group B and C constitute those who are indirectly involved, with group C including a category as vague that extend broader than “sympathisers” (C2), which is “the masses” (C3). Political detainees and prisoners of group B were the people who are exiled to Buru Island (for men) or Plantungan Island (for women) where they were imprisoned and forced labour.¹¹²

One significant attempt to reclaim the collective memory of the Genosida '65 is through the recognition and preservation of mass graves and/or execution sites. My choice to focus on mass graves specifically acknowledges how the G30S metanarrative, which claims hegemony over the collective memory, spotlights Lubang Buaya as an execution site.

¹¹¹ Kusumaningrum et al., 'Sites of Violence, Sites of Peace, Sites of Justice', 311; Wardaya, 'Menembus Politik Ingatan', 168.

¹¹² Hardoyo, 'The Future of the Left in Indonesia', 158.

As such, I find it most appropriate to address narratives of Genosida '65 through its sites of brutality and grief, execution sites, mass graves.

In 2016, President Jokowi requested that the Coordinating Minister for Political, Legal, and Security Affairs (*Menkopolhukam*) of the time, Luhut Binsar Pandjaitan, locate the mass graves of the "1965 events" victims. However, Luhut inadequately responded to this request. Amidst the polemics surrounding apologies for gross human rights violations, including Genosida '65, Luhut framed the request as a challenging task, stating that the government could only apologize to the victims if the mass graves were found. In a display of pre-emptive disbelief, he requested civil society organizations (CSOs) and civilians to indicate the exact locations of these mass graves, claiming that no results were garnered.¹¹³

As an effort to reclaim the overlooked sites of violence and memories of Genosida '65, this chapter will be based on counter-geography¹¹⁴ and embedded memory¹¹⁵, in respect to the local social context, of execution sites or mass graves I visited in Yogyakarta, its East Java surroundings, and Bali. These site visits are part of my attempt to create my own space to challenge the collective memory hegemony of the G30S metanarrative. As I present Genosida '65 narratives I noted from my fieldwork, I attempt to address the second research question on how collective memory hegemony held by G30S metanarrative is being challenged or contested in public space.

2.1. Toer '65: A light-hearted attempt to say "ziarah"

¹¹³ 'Jokowi perintahkan pencarian kuburan massal korban peristiwa 1965'. Luhut claims that despite being open to information regarding the location of the mass graves, not a single mass grave was reported to him or the ministry which is in complete dissonance to the reality of CSOs, civilians, and documentaries reporting the locations.

¹¹⁴ Kusumaningrum et al., 'Sites of Violence, Sites of Peace, Sites of Justice'.

¹¹⁵ Leksana, *Memory Culture of the Anti-Leftist Violence in Indonesia*.

The state-endorsed collective memory hegemony of the G30S metanarrative centring the execution site of Lubang Buaya, shifts attention and casts a looming shadow over countless other sites of brutalities and execution of Genosida '65. Almost all the mass grave sites associated with Genosida '65 are established/recognised and maintained by communities at the local level without formal government acknowledgement.¹¹⁶ These memory sites are sustained by its sociality and collective effort of the community, as such they become more meaningful to the locals. While these sites are often an "open secret" among locals,¹¹⁷ outsiders (whether geographically or network-wise) find it difficult to discern their whereabouts.

In the beginning of my fieldwork I first met Rangga Purbaya (Mas Rangga) through my *Budhe*¹¹⁸ who is a family friend and a member of the Dialita, a choir group consisting of women survivors or *keluarga korban* of Genosida '65.¹¹⁹ He was introduced to me as the person who could help locate mass graves of victims of Genosida '65 in Yogyakarta. During our initial conversation, I learned that he was one of the five people who initiated and manage "Faith in Speculation '65" (FIS '65), a collective that spatially tracks memories and personal narratives of Genosida '65 on a map.¹²⁰

Mas Rangga introduced me to the concept of "*Toer* '65," a play on words with "tour" and Pramoedya Ananda Toer, referring to informal excursions he and sometimes his colleagues in FIS '65 conduct with interested people (usually researchers) to explore and

¹¹⁶ Leksana, *Memory Culture of the Anti-Leftist Violence in Indonesia*; Wahyuningroem, 'Seducing for Truth and Justice'; Hearman, *Unmarked Graves*; Dirgantoro, 'From Silence to Speech', 303; *Pengakuan Algojo 1965: Investigasi Tempo Perihal Pembantaian 1965*.

¹¹⁷ Roosa, 'The State of Knowledge about an Open Secret'.

¹¹⁸ Javanese for "Auntie".

¹¹⁹ Lestariningsih and Sunarti, 'Dialita'; Mulia, 'The Dialita Choir'; Putra, 'Dialita, Ibu-ibu Korban 1965 yang "Bersuara" Lewat Nada'; Setyawan, 'Dialita Choir and the Struggle to Fight the Nation's Amnesia - Academia'.

¹²⁰ Purbaya and Stevy, 'FAITH IN SPECULATIONS'.

identify sites related to the memory of Genosida '65. In our private two-person “Toer,” we visited several locations: Luweng Grubug, Rowo Jombor, Klaten, and sites in Yogyakarta.

Figure 2.1. Luweng Jomblang¹²¹ tourism information board showing the underground passage connecting it with Luweng Grubug (Photo by author).

The first site we visited took us by the midst of a forest in Gunung Kidul regency, Yogyakarta. We came to the area specifically for Luweng Grubug, the deepest vertical cave on Java Island leading to an underground river. At the bottom, the light entering Luweng Grubug creates a striking visual phenomenon of heavenly lights shining from above. As such, the bottom of Luweng Grubug is a well-beloved spot for tourists. Despite this, tourists that want to experience its beauty only has one option to venture the location which is to climb down from a nearby vertical cave called Luweng Jomblang. Tourists are manually lowered

¹²¹ In English: “Grubug Cave”. “*Luweng*” is a Javanese word for “cave”. This title for Luweng Grubug and Luweng Jomblang will not be italicised as it is the popular name to refer to the location.

down for forty metres by local people working for the sole tourism group, then they would need to go through an underground horizontal passage that connects the two vertical caves to end up at the bottom of Luweng Grubug. Similarly, tourists would need to detour and be pulled up with the contraption through the same way from Luweng Jomblang in order to exit.

Figure 2.2. Top of Luweng Jomblang and its pulley contraption (Photo by author).

Figure 2.3. View from the top of Luweng Jomblang (Photo by author).

Figure 2.4. View from the top of Luweng Grubug (Photo by author).

From the very top, the visual contrast between the two caves is striking: Luweng Jomblang is open and bright (Figure 2.3), while Luweng Grubug is enclosed and hidden within the forest (Figure 2.4).

To reach Luweng Grubug, Mas Rangga and I parked at the only tourist accommodation located a few minutes away after passing the last house of the Pancarejo Semanu village. It was the only house-like structures amidst the forest greens.

It was then a 7 minutes' walk into the forest packed with many young teak trees, past the locals' gardens and plantations. As there were no clear pathways through overgrown vegetations and tall trees, I was told that the guidance to Luweng Grubug is identifiable by locating a collection of trees that were of somewhat discernibly darker shades of green in the distance. I am convinced that if I did not know exactly what to look for, I would not be able to visually locate Luweng Grubug, as Figure 2.5 can attest to how the site is barely discernible apart from the rest of the forest.

Figure 2.5. Luweng Grubug from the left-hand side, the dark part on the left is the mouth (cliff) of the vertical cave (Photo by author).

Figure 2.6. Top of Luweng Grubug and its metal contraption to climb down (Photo by author).

Figure 2.7. Luweng Grubug downward view from the top edge (Photo by author).

At the top of Luweng Grubug, a square concrete box (visible in Figure 2.5 on the right-hand side) and metal contraption (Figure 2.6) mark the cliff's edge used by hikers to climb to the cave's bottom 90 metres down. From the top, Luweng Grubug looks unassuming and rather narrow at approximately 4-5 metres in diameter across, a jarring difference to Luweng Jomblang which diameter is said to be 50 meters across. The contrast of vastness and closed-off ness between Luweng Jomblang and Luweng Grubug possibly

influenced the decision as to why the executions took place in the latter than the former, as Luweng Grubug is physically more enclosed, secretive, and local people would not be able to see. I held to the metal contraption trying to peek down, only to see pitch blackness as pictured in Figure 2.7. Although from the top it looks narrow, it is said that Luweng Grubug is approximately the size of a football field at the bottom.

It was here that Mas Rangga detailed how executions were carried out. Prisoners, tied together by a rope, were pushed into the cave, causing those behind to follow suit. He contrasted this execution story with our pathway through the village, noting how prisoners would pass the last house of the village before facing their death in the forest at Luweng Grubug.¹²²

Cliffside execution is one of the common methods of execution carried throughout Genosida '65.¹²³ Another popular execution site being running rivers which carry bodies all the way to the beach shore. Such method of execution is known to have painted many rivers across the country red with blood, bodies clogging streams, up to the point of sanitation issues at the time.¹²⁴ Luweng Grubug offers both as the vertical cave leads down to an underground river that has a rapid flow.

Aside from the metal contraption for the hikers to climb down, there was no discernible sign that indicates Luweng Grubug's existence from afar, let alone its identity as an execution site or mass grave. Up-close, however, was a worn-down cloth tied to a tree at the left-hand edge most part of the cliff by the metal contraption which Mas Rangga

¹²² Perpustakaan Online Genosida 1965-1966, 'Kuburan Massal '65 (The Killing Field)'; Susmayanti and Kriesdinar, 'Gua Grubug, Saksi Pembantaian Mengerikan PKI di Gunungkidul'; Tugu Jogja, 'Luweng Grubug, Gua di Gunungkidul yang Konon Jadi Tempat Eksekusi Pengikut PKI'.

¹²³ Tempo, *Pengakuan Algojo 1965: Investigasi Tempo Perihal Pembantaian 1965*, 68; Tempo, 72; Perpustakaan Online Genosida 1965-1966, 'Kuburan Massal '65 (The Killing Field)'.

¹²⁴ SENYAP - *The Look of Silence*; Dadang Christanto; 'Buried in the Beach'; Silalahi, 'Mitos Sungai Ular'.

informed me originated from his colleague in 2022. He shared that they made attempts to memorialize the site with *Kamboja* flowers¹²⁵, local villagers likely uprooted them to maintain the area's tourism appeal. The cave tourism is a significant part of the villagers' economy, and marking Luweng Grubug as an execution site could negatively impact tourism.

¹²⁵ Kamboja flowers loosely hold significance in Indonesia as the flower used for death-related ceremonies.

Figure 2.8.-2.9. Dadang Christanto's installation on his *ziarah* to Luweng Grubug¹²⁶

¹²⁶ Perpustakaan Online Genosida 1965-1966, '[Situs Genosida 1965-1966] Ziarah, Doa dan Tabur Bunga Di Luweng Grubug, Gunung Kidul.'

Nonetheless, families of survivors continue to visit Luweng Grubug for *ziarah*¹²⁷ to pray and remember their loved ones. Villagers can easily identify visitors there for 1965-related reasons, as it's either the same group of people or evident from their behavior. Luweng Grubug has become the site for grieving and *ziarah* of Genosida '65's *keluarga korban* throughout the years.¹²⁸

Figure 2.10. Rowo Jombor logo on the dam's sidewalk (Photo by author).

¹²⁷ *Ziarah* in Indonesia is an act of pilgrimage or visit to a sacred place. It indicates spiritual purpose and include forms paying respect or praying to those who passed away. *Ziarah* to graves (or *ziarah kubur*) is mostly observed by families of the deceased.

¹²⁸ BAK; *LAGU UNTUK ANAKKU - Film Dokumenter*; Perpustakaan Online Genosida 1965-1966, '[Situs Genosida 1965-1966] Ziarah, Doa dan Tabur Bunga Di Luweng Grubug, Gunung Kidul.'

Figure 2.11. Rowo Jombor (Photo by author).

The second site we visited was a dam on the outskirts of Yogyakarta. Mas Rangga explained that the prisoners of Genosida '65 were forced to build the dam and were executed upon completion, their bodies would later be integrated into the structure by the other prisoners. In other words, as we walked along the edge of the dam, he pointed out that we were essentially walking on a mass grave.

As sediments built up along the dam's sides, dredging around the edges of the dam became commonplace. During these dredging operations, skeletal remains and bones of those executed are frequently unearthed. This is not surprising to the locals, as the dark history of the dam's construction is well-known in the area and became more of an open secret.

Mas Ranga contrasted this location with Luweng Grubug, noting that because the dam is not a tourism site, it was easier to hear stories from local people about the genocide. The dam was surrounded by *warung* (small food stalls/restaurants), to which he and his colleagues would strike up conversations with local villagers who would then share how the executions during the dam's construction became a spectacle that people gathered to watch.

In Klaten, a regency outside Yogyakarta known for its historical PKI support, we visited the only known physical memorial for Genosida '65 victims in the area. Known as a "red city" due to its historical support for the PKI, discussing Genosida '65 is comparatively not so much of a taboo in Klaten than in the other areas we visited.

Figure 2.12. Grave-shaped memorial at Karanganom (Photo by author).

In Karanganom sub-district, under a small bridge over a narrow river, is the first memorial structure of a Genosida '65 mass grave that I had seen. The memorial, constructed with grey concrete, mirrors the structural outline of a traditional Indonesian grave. It is straightforward and unmistakably a grave, even to those unfamiliar with the Genosida '65 context. The site itself is said to be the site to the execution of approximately seven individuals. It was suspected that the memorial was built by family members of one of the victims.

On our way back from Klaten, Mas Rangga had explained that most, if not all, old bridges from the 1960s still standing today are likely mass grave sites. When I asked why there are fewer bridges now, he explained that many of the rivers have dried up or shrunk significantly over time. Standing by the small river next to the memorial, it was hard to imagine it as a significant waterway, but I could envision the larger, faster current it might have had in the 1960s.

Figure 2.13. Gedung Jefferson¹²⁹ as Biznet office per 2024 (Photo by author).

Figure 2.14. Revitalisation sign in front of Benteng Vredeborg¹³⁰ (Photo by author).

¹²⁹ In English: “Jefferson Building”.

¹³⁰ In English: “Vredeborg Fort”.

The next day, we stayed and explored Yogyakarta city with two destinations in mind. Our first stop was the Biznet office, a telecom company housed in a fresh, modern, almost futuristic building. Standing there, it was hard to imagine that this site, formerly known as the Thomas Jefferson Building, was one of the most brutal sites during Genosida '65.¹³¹

The Biznet building, previously known as Gedung Jefferson was used for the interrogation and torture of prisoners during the genocide. Notoriously, the current office parking lot once housed a three-times-four metres shed where dead bodies were collected until they were disposed of.

Our second intended visit was to the Benteng Vredeburg, a former Dutch colonial fortress, repurposed to an Indonesian history museum located at the popular Malioboro street. Unbeknownst to most of its visitors, Benteng Vredeburg was a former prison and house of torture for the prisoners of Genosida '65. Unfortunately, we were not able to enter the premises as the entire Benteng Vredeburg complex was closed for revitalisation. However, I noticed on the construction banner the visualized plans for the revitalisation fort, which in one part displayed Suharto's name prominently within a list of names at the new planned entrance to the museum in the complex.

Yogyakarta is a city I visit at least once a year, and this year I visited it on three separate occasions. The act of revisiting old sites and exploring new ones with counter narratives from Mas Rangga was a powerful way to rebuild the relationship between my memory and the spatial surroundings that hold them through remembering. At one point of our journey, I was reminded of one of the summers I spent in Kepulauan Seribu, to which

¹³¹ *Derita, Stigma, Dan 'dosa Turunan' Anak Cucu Mantan Tapol '65; In Defiance, 2016; In Defiance, 2016; Perpustakaan Online Genosida 1965-1966, 'Gedung Jefferson Yogyakarta'.*

my father had shared on how he could never visit Kepulauan Seribu as the seas were used as a massive site to dispose of bodies during Orde Baru.

2.2. Taman '65

In Denpasar, Bali, lives a memorial that turned itself into a community and community space, known as “Taman 65”.¹³² I had the opportunity to speak with Ika Alvania (Ika) who is one of the people who manages Taman 65.

¹³² In English, “*taman*” translates to “park”.

Figure 2.15. Taman 65 and I Gusti Made Raka's statue. From left to right: Bu Mayun, author, and Ika Alvania (Photo by author).

Taman 65 is established in the yard of Agung Alit (Aji Alit) and is centred around the statue of I Gusti Made Raka, the father to Bu Mayun, Aji Degung, and Aji Alit. The family, known for hosting parties and celebrations, has cultivated strong relationships with their neighbours, a crucial factor given the close-knit nature and proximity of Balinese housing. Upon entering the open space of Taman 65, I was greeted by the full-size graffiti on the wall perpendicular to where the statue was located. The graffiti presented a depiction of a Balinese Goddess holding a rifle and fast-food items, looming over the land of Bali which was covered with snarky signs; in totality a commentary on how capitalism and its developmentalist tourism-focused gentrification has consumed the Goddess and consequently corrupted the land of Bali, which is well known as the "island of Gods".

In its advent, Taman 65 started by slowly screening commercial movies that touch upon the context of Genosida '65 such as "*Gie*". This strategy of choosing commercial movies helped avoid opposition since these films were not banned but commercially available in public theatres. Ika mentioned they have stopped events explicitly about Genosida '65 due to the trauma it caused older community members.

Although Taman '65 has produced some documentation, such as a short film on memory and music with former political prisoners, their focus remains on education rather than documentation effort. This educational emphasis is exemplified by facilitating study tours, sometimes guided by Genosida '65 survivors, with international or foreign schools learning history. These tours would include visits to former and present detention centres such as the one in Pekambangan and Kerobokan, providing a tangible connection to history.

The recent “*Tur ‘65*” bike tour, conducted openly amidst the tourist influx, contrasts starkly with the more secretive tours in Luweng Grubug. This openness highlights the adaptive strategies of memory activism in different contexts, in which the bustling tourism industry aids specifically in enabling counter-narrative tours such as this one to be carried out in public with less risk. Ika noted that although locals might recognize the Genosida ‘65 focus of these tours when they visit memory sites, the locals generally do not confront them. She shared that asking someone's age can be an effective way to start a conversation about Genosida ‘65 with locals, subtly acknowledging the historical context.

Ika emphasised the Taman 65 goal is to spark curiosity in the younger generation. This extends to *Taman Baca Kesiman*¹³³ (TBK), a reading park and café founded by Agung Alit and his wife. TBK contains a collection of leftist literature, including works by Pramoedya Ananta Toer, difficult to obtain in Indonesia. This library, in the middle of paddy fields, offers a space for reflection and learning.

As I bid my temporary farewell to Bu Mayun, Ika, and Taman 65, I noticed a large *Kamboja* tree looming over the park. Given *Kamboja*'s association with death and memorialization, I asked if its placement was intentional. Although Ika did not think it was deliberate, I still found the tree's presence adds a layer of symbolic resonance to the space.

2.3. Countering hegemony, countering geography

As a response to the second research question pertaining to the way collective memory hegemony over Genosida ‘65 can be contested in public space, I refer to my fieldwork in saying that there are two interconnected layers to contesting collective

¹³³ In English: “Kesiman Reading Park/Garden”

memory hegemony. They are separate and not ordered in a particular sequence of which one happens first, but one cannot happen without the other.

The first layer is the social, in the introduction of counter-narratives. The “*Toer ‘65*” I took with Mas Ranga is the example of this. The “tour” method of having him tell me narratives about the spaces we visited that are not visible, due to lack of physical markers or descriptors, is similar to one used by Kusumaningrum et al. in their project, to which they refer to as “counter-geography”.¹³⁴ Counter-geography can be understood as the form of introducing counter-narrative that challenges dominant narratives on a particular site through tour formats.

“Sites of Violence, Sites of Peace” project by Kusumaningrum et al. in Yogyakarta explored this mean of activation specifically through city tour between university students, LGBT youth group, and *Kipper (Kiprah Perempuan)*¹³⁵ which then create relational encounter and rewriting of the cityscapes which creates a form of counter-geography through the testimonies of the *Kipper* women.¹³⁶ In other words, memory sites play a crucial role in the social reclamation of genocide memory by sharing their narratives about particular spaces and further bringing light to embedded memory—the memory of violence within everyday spatial realities.¹³⁷

Tours are unique in the way that it can socially reclaim genocide memory through developing counter-narratives into spaces creating counter-geography. More than that, using tours for counter-geography also create a new space within the memory sites for relational encounters that build new individual relations to the people (with the survivors,

¹³⁴ Kusumaningrum et al., ‘Sites of Violence, Sites of Peace, Sites of Justice’.

¹³⁵ Community of Genosida ‘65 women survivors.

¹³⁶ Kusumaningrum et al., ‘Sites of Violence, Sites of Peace, Sites of Justice’, 310.

¹³⁷ Leksana, ‘Embedded Remembering’; Kusumaningrum et al., ‘Sites of Violence, Sites of Peace, Sites of Justice’, 310; Strassler, ‘Fragments of Memory’.

the people you go on tour with). From the “Sites of Violence, Sites of Peace” project, Indonesian students who were previously unaware of the degree of violence women detainees go through due to Genosida ’65 developed relationship not just to the space itself but also to the survivors who shared their narratives in this tour. Such relational encounter established or reaffirmed the foundation to building sympathy and solidarity to the survivors of Genosida ’65. This can be seen from a student in the project who encountered their personal experience of “remembering” when they expressed sympathy to the survivors, signalling the possibility that the way they recognise the survivors have shifted, possibly from the caricature of PKI (who are framed as those persecuted with Genosida ’65) that prevails alongside G30S metanarrative.¹³⁸

Despite its perks, counter-geography through tours is ephemeral and limited in a way that it is exclusive to the few people who can access and embark on them, of course also acknowledging how this ephemerality plays in favour to the privacy and safety concerns of some survivors who would participate. With that, I believe mediums such as done by “imagetexts” concept of *Setiaphari ’65* and the map of FIS ’65 help supplement the permanence of counter-geography effort.¹³⁹

The other layer to contesting the collective memory hegemony is individual or at the very least more personal. It pertains the act of creating a space in which you can remember; in other words, challenging the hegemony on a personal level entails the act of remembering. When I say “individual” and “personal”, it does not mean that it is completely isolated from sociality, rather it focuses on the individual or personal. This layer reflects on remembering and creating the space to remember, both acts require drive from within the

¹³⁸ Kusumaningrum et al., ‘Sites of Violence, Sites of Peace, Sites of Justice’, 318.

¹³⁹ Strassler, ‘Fragments of Memory’, 90; ‘1965setiaphari • Instagram Photos and Videos’; ‘#living1965’; Purbaya and Stevy, ‘FAITH IN SPECULATIONS’.

person. Countering hegemony cannot start through force, one would need to have the drive within themselves to initiate it. The social can inspire it, but it would not necessarily activate the layer. Whether it be picking up books that are not part of the dominant narrative or visiting memory sites, this layer is cardinal.

To engage in memory site visits, let alone counter-geographical tours, means to be entangled within the community of Genosida '65. The reason is that identifying the sites' location require retroactive connection to the network, and because a single site shares not just one individual story but rather already containing multitudes of different narratives and accounts of the past violence. As such, it is to be understood that community's main role in the continuity of collective memory is not something deliberate. It is automatic, active, and alive.

Collective memory, as Leksana notes, is both dynamic and is continuously sustained by social interactions.¹⁴⁰ The preservation of collective memory is a social endeavour that keeps it relevant and serves as a means of healing collective trauma. Memory sites hold significance that goes beyond dictating a singular narrative in the name of "truth"; rather they serve as a social site for people to see themselves, their families, their trauma, and to move towards a path of interpersonal or personal reconciliation. As such, memory sites play this integral role in the effort to countering hegemony as they become the hub for remembering and perpetual preservation of collective memory by mean of activation. In the public space, the collective memory hegemony over Genosida '65 can be contested through the act of remembering, through social experience such as counter-geography (in the form

¹⁴⁰ Leksana, *Memory Culture of the Anti-Leftist Violence in Indonesia*.

of tours, among others) and individual experience through the reflection of the social or personal pursuits.

Chapter 3 : Where all the banned books are

“*Perpustakaan Online Genosida ‘65*” (hereafter: POG ‘65 or the online archive) is the first non-Wikipedia site that came up on the search engine when I looked up the keywords “Genosida ‘65”. It was also where I began my journey in conducting my research on Genosida ‘65. In the site, I discovered a multitude of entries, not only pertaining to the genocide but also documenting various human rights abuses in Indonesia that were challenging to find elsewhere. Initially, my goal was to approach POG ‘65 through the Appadurain understanding of an electronic archive.¹⁴¹ I aimed to develop a deeper understanding and establish a connection with it as a deliberate collective social project focused on remembering and preserving the memory of Indonesia's past, especially in the case of the Genosida ‘65. However, throughout the months, the social dimension of POG ‘65 unfolded before my eyes in ways that I had not initially anticipated.

This chapter attempts to delineate my three-months exploration of the POG ‘65 landscape as an online archive in two segments. The first part, I bore my findings on the materiality as well my narrative of exploring the depths of the archive. The latter part, I shift my focus to the distinct themes discerned within the ethnographical landscape of the online archive: mutuality and memory.

3.1. To enter a “forest” of POG ‘65 willingly

Upon my first encounter with the POG ‘65 website, I was greeted by a quote that proudly takes up space: “*kebenaran dan kemanusiaan tak bisa dibungkam*”.¹⁴² The site, which was completely foreign to me, evoked a similar feeling to discovering Pramodya

¹⁴¹ Appadurai, ‘Archive and Aspiration’.

¹⁴² In English: “truth and humanity cannot be silenced” from Foundation on the Victims of the 1965 Killings (YPKP ‘65). Immediately I thought of Fajar Merah’s song “kebenaran akan terus hidup”, and consequently the weight and centrality the word *kebenaran* holds within Indonesian resistance.

Ananta Toer's book displayed in a public cafe, a discreet signalling of a "safe" space for minds opposing the dominant state narrative of history.

I was overwhelmed by the extensive display of entries that follow under the quotation. The first entry pinned to the top left of the page displays the "bibliography" of the POG '65. Next to it, in chronological descending order, are entries that fill up the aforementioned bibliography, the most recent one being just from a few days' prior.¹⁴³

Regular interaction with POG '65 seemed to entail a few hours within my days as it drags me (willingly) into a rabbit hole where I am immersed in new or detailed information, I never thought I would be curious about. Most of the information in POG '65 is not reactionary but rather speaks to a distinct absence or silence. Until now, I am still in awe with the organisation and upkeep of POG '65, how one would know and address the existence of an absence.

POG '65 anticipates my questions, revealing a disconcerting awareness of the substantial gaps in my understanding despite presumptions of positionality that privileges me in acknowledging Indonesia's past violence. It introduces me to absences, gaps, silences I was not aware of; it feels as though I am speaking to survivors or other *keluarga korban* silently through my screen. When I approach the online archive without starting from the bibliography, I find myself mirroring my perception of the entries—scattered and spread in spatial positions that are difficult to articulate outwardly.

On days I approach POG '65 with a more specific goal, I start my journey from its pinned bibliography. Relying on my browser search function to look up keywords, a few clicks lead me to relevant tabs on my browser. Gloria Truly Estrelita (Truly) likened "POG

¹⁴³ Throughout my time interacting with POG '65, the latest entry would always be only within a few days prior, if not a little over a week, exemplifying the online archive's vitality and perhaps also Andreas Iswinarto, who is the sole creator and manager of the entire online archive.

'65" to a "forest", describing the navigation in the online archive as "like walking through a forest, one needs to want to *jalan-jalan* inside of it". Perhaps we share the same experience when navigating through POG '65. Similar to my fieldwork visits, I find that entering with intention and a clear mind yields the sought goodness. On the other hand, Lea Pamungkas (Lea) attributed the relative easiness of navigation to her familiarity with the topic of '65; navigating becomes easier when you know what you are seeking, departing not from absence but from a question.¹⁴⁴

3.2. Materiality of POG '65: Mimesis of documentation and its shape

As an online archive, I perceive POG '65's materiality through its shape in entirety and attributing it to two things: scatter and spread. Aside from the scatter and spread that overlaps within the variety of entries POG '65 holds entries, which includes different events of human rights abuses, mostly throughout Orde Baru Indonesia, the online archive displays mimesis to the Indonesian archival landscape.

Structural archival work of the leftist movement in pre-Reformasi Indonesia is scattered around different countries, with many residing in the International Institute of Social Histories (IISH) in the Netherlands to be "safeguarded". In Indonesia, military archives that carry the legacy of violent military operations in the country, such as the Regional Military Command Centre (KOTI) archive, remain classified and can only be accessed by researchers through a lengthy process of attaining official permission.¹⁴⁵ As of now, within this context, the Indonesian National Archive (ANRI) only publicly possesses archives of the organisations that were banned throughout *Orde Baru*.¹⁴⁶

¹⁴⁴ Pamungkas, Online Interview 4.

¹⁴⁵ Theo, Online Interview 3; Theo, 'The PKI Archives and the Need for More Inclusive Descriptions by Rika Theo - Blog | IISG'.

¹⁴⁶ Theo, Online Interview 3; Hirsch, 'The Generation of Postmemory'.

Rika Theo (Rika), a trained archivist dedicated to Indonesian archival efforts and Genosida '65 community, expressed frustration with this struggle of documentation, citing it resulting in the absence of both memory and imagination of the current Indonesian people of Indonesian leftist movement history.¹⁴⁷ This absence, due to the scatter and spread, helps enable the Orde Baru state-endorsed metanarrative on PKI and G30S to prevail as the dominant narrative dictating leftist history.

3.3. Expanding postmemory and witness through “family”

The persistent grip of the dominant narrative of the left movement by the authoritarian Orde Baru regime restricted the Reformasi youth, limiting their conception of history to a singular, state-driven perspective. Instead of just creating a static horizontal memory gap, it creates a memory gap that extends intergenerationally. To address this, the notion of expanding witnesses becomes crucial.¹⁴⁸

Through Hirsch's concept of postmemory neologism which provides tools to cultivate a strategy in transmitting the memory of the past, there is a possibility to enable the expansion of the scope of witnesses to include posthumous voices and presence in different manifestations.¹⁴⁹ POG '65 exemplifies the practice of bridging memory, not passively but as a hub that creates connections between those who choose to interact with it. Within this context, by implementing an understanding of a family to Indonesian human rights activists, meaning those seen as part of the solidarity struggle rather than biological connections, POG '65 bridges the gap through expanding the conception of family that allows for the postmemory process of intergenerational transmission of memory.¹⁵⁰

¹⁴⁷ Theo, 'The PKI Archives and the Need for More Inclusive Descriptions by Rika Theo - Blog | IISG'.

¹⁴⁸ Estrelita, Personal Communication at Pau.

¹⁴⁹ Hirsch, 'The Generation of Postmemory'.

¹⁵⁰ Lee, *Activist Archives*.

In between these changing tides of memory in Indonesia, survivors, *keluarga korban*, people standing in solidarity disperse to uphold a structure of memory and remembering. When others are tired, look away, and the face of the ghost dissipates, they maintain what they can with what they have and who they have.

3.4. Mutuality and the ethnography that sustains an archive

Andreas Iswinarto's archival effort with POG '65 embodies the spirit of Appadurai and Foucauldian principles, liberating the archive from being a quiescent site of memory and imbuing it with vitality by making the online archive a collective deliberate project.¹⁵¹ This is palpable through the accounts of the POG '65 interviewees and their interactions with him regarding their shared effort for the cause of '65. In discussing the way Truly contributed to his work with POG '65, she informed me when relevant references given to him, in hopes of being shared through the online archive, were always redirected somewhere else in the case of them being turned down. In other words, he would suggest alternative avenues or platforms to share those references.¹⁵²

Outside of conversations with Andreas on casual inquiries regarding the content of POG '65, most of the interviewees confessed that they have never had a proper conversation specifically on this online archive.¹⁵³ Nevertheless, all of them have an open private communication channel with Andreas respectively. It is the case that they do not feel the necessity to particularly discuss POG '65.

Dadang Christanto (Dadang), an Indonesian artist known for his works on Genosida '65 and other past violence by the country, described entries of his art which Andreas

¹⁵¹ Appadurai, 'Archive and Aspiration'; Weld, 'Archival Culture, State Secrets, and the Archive Wars'.

¹⁵² Estrelita, Online Interview 2.

¹⁵³ Pamungkas, Online Interview 4; Theo, Online Interview 3; Christanto, Online Interview 1.

created and POG '65 entries Dadang shares, do not particularly necessitate communication between the two of them. “[we do it] without permission, like we both know. Because we mutually share, we are heading towards the same path, like we are the same frequency”. This silent knowing amity was also described by Lea’s account that highlights the unspoken mutual trust that amounts to her assumption that they share a common understanding of the online archive. “[Andreas] trusts me, I trust him, *ya begitu saja*.”¹⁵⁴ She shared how in the last ten years of Andreas working on POG '65, they never had a proper talk specifically of POG '65 despite having their documentation efforts overlap, between Lea’s management of the “Friends of Peoples Tribunal” private Facebook group and Andreas’ POG '65. “(...) *dan kami gak pernah ngobrol. Ya kami saling mengisi aja, bahwa kita sama-sama punya pengertian*.”¹⁵⁵ Maybe we share the same ideology about the leftist movement, even though we have never talked [about it]. Like I said, it’s just organic.”¹⁵⁶

Respecting Appadurai’s understanding of the archive as a “social project,”¹⁵⁷ the social dimension in which the online archive is entangled plays different distinct roles for the online archive as a subject. Firstly, POG '65 acts as a unifying force between '65 communities engaged in various aspects such as remembrance and advocacy. Secondly, the social network in which the online archive finds itself provides a degree of security for its continuity, primarily operating on the notion of mutuality.

3.5. Reclaiming collective memory through archiving

The year 2023 in Indonesia marks a critical juncture as the nation grapples with the recurring spectre of past human rights violations. President Joko Widodo's acknowledgment

¹⁵⁴ Italic part in English: “yeah just like that.”

¹⁵⁵ Italic part in English: “and we (Lea and Andreas) never talked. We just connect the dots on how both of us share an understanding (...)”

¹⁵⁶ Pamungkas, Online Interview 4.

¹⁵⁷ Appadurai, ‘Archive and Aspiration’.

of historical abuses, including the 1965 genocide, initiates a crucial dialogue. However, the cyclical nature of memory and the reluctance to confront an authoritarian past persist.

Within this complex landscape, POG '65 emerges as a unique digital archive, offering a profound exploration of Genosida '65 collective memory and speaking for its reclamation. Navigating POG '65 reveals not only a scattered yet interconnected tapestry of entries but also the power to challenge preconceived notions and unveil the profound awareness of absences and silences. In this way, POG '65 social landscape reflects the reality of Genosida '65 collective memory and the collective efforts to sustain it despite the shadow casted by G30S metanarrative.

As POG '65 functions as a social project, the ephemerality of online archives is counteracted by the social dimension that operates on mutuality fostered by Andreas and expanding of Hirsch's postmemory concept with the Indonesian activist culture. This collective effort transcends individual contributions, fostering a shared commitment to preserving Indonesia's untold history. In the ever-changing tides of memory, POG '65 stands resilient—a dynamic force sustaining the structure of remembering.

Conclusion

The endeavour of writing this research is a difficult one, mainly due to my positionality to the topic. Regardless, foremost I would like us to go over the questions and answers laid out throughout the thesis before closing with a reflection.

First, the G30S metanarrative overshadows the memory of Genosida '65, establishing a collective memory hegemony under Orde Baru. This metanarrative provided legitimacy to both the Orde Baru regime and the events of Genosida '65, effectively becoming the foundation on which the regime was built. Questioning this metanarrative equates to challenging the regime itself. The Lubang Buaya complex, with its dioramas and slogans, immortalises the ceaseless pursuit of intrusively insisting G30S metanarrative as "*kebenaran*" and to sustain its collective memory hegemony.

With how much the current hegemon focuses on execution site and brutalistic torture, it seems most appropriate for me to shift the discussion to other execution sites in the coming months or years as part of Genosida '65.

Second, after grappling with the pain and limitations imposed by the G30S metanarrative, I attempted to remedy this by shifting the conversation to how this hegemony can be challenged in public spaces, or in other words to reclaim the collective memory of Genosida '65. I found that before all else, establishing a personal layer of remembering, creating a space for oneself to remember is essential to do so. This personal layer is interdependent with the social layer, which introduces counter-geography as a method to share counter-narratives on memory sites and provides a social space for relational encounters. By challenging the hegemony in this way, it is possible to also establish and reaffirm sympathy and solidarity with survivors and the *keluarga korban* of Genosida '65.

Lastly, through the archival ethnography research on POG '65, I found how efforts in countering hegemony and reclaiming collective memory creates its own network that upholds the respective efforts. Although initially I was aiming to explore POG '65 materiality more so than anything else, it ended up unfolding of a larger dimension of social network that manages to uphold the ambitious project such of POG '65. Aside from creating its own networks to counter hegemony and consequently reclaim collective memory, POG '65 also unifies the different Genosida '65 collectives that create the larger community. This new social network secures its continuity through social mutuality between the founder (in this case, Andreas) and others.

As such, I stress that remembering starts within oneself and is then shared. Remembering as an act of resistance is the smallest yet a powerful form of resistance amid many restrictions. This makes remembering difficult to methodologically approach or witness as an outsider, as it is an incredibly personal act.

Despite that, this thesis attests that it is possible to write about it.

Learning more about the G30S metanarrative filled me with frustration. For months, I was surrounded by slogans framing the kidnappings as the most inhuman tragedy in Indonesia's past, capitalised by the state and the TNI. The maintenance of sites like the Lubang Buaya complex, the cowardly reluctance to address past human rights abuses, and the comedically symbolic support for remnants of Orde Baru violence, such as Jokowi's awarding Prabowo, an inactive military general, the honorary four-star general rank,¹⁵⁸ perpetuate this frustration.

¹⁵⁸ Hamida, 'Prabowo Subianto Terima Penghargaan Jenderal Bintang 4, Kronologinya?'; Lamb, 'Indonesia Awards Presumed next President Prabowo Rank of Four-Star General'.

I am angry. But I want to present this thesis as a hope, to show how countless other Indonesians including myself remember Genosida '65.

The community of Genosida '65, who initiated and sustain collective efforts for a true collective memory unclouded by TNI's G30S metanarrative hegemony, enabled this thesis. Despite hearing valid concerns from almost all my correspondences of how efforts pertaining Genosida '65 may not be sustainable, I echo Wiji Thukul's words: "*aku akan tetap ada dan berlipat ganda.*" I am far from the only Reformasi youth working on this topic. The Genosida '65 social network is constantly refreshed in each collective effort. Your act of remembering Genosida '65 is enough. It is resistance.

For those with Indonesian governmental power reading my thesis, understand that continuous denial of state-acknowledged memorials to *keluarga korban* and *penyintas* of Genosida '65 does not suppress the memory of violence. It does not kill it either. Even as the survivors pass away, it will continue to live. For there to be an attempt to open space for Genosida '65 collective memory without centring the G30S metanarrative or infantile caricature of PKI, such as revoking TAP MPRS No. XXV/MPRS/1966, would open avenues to address and mend not just the past, but also the ongoing violence against those affected by the Orde Baru regime at large. As my final reiteration, just like this thesis, it is the first step, not the last.

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